

D2.1: State of the art review

[WP2 – Genomics: ethical, legal and social analysis]

Lead contributor	Heidi Howard, Emilia Niemiec, Alexandra Soulier (Uppsala University) heidi.howard@crb.uu.se , emilia.niemiec@crb.uu.se , alexandra.soulier@crb.uu.se
Other contributors	-This report was reviewed by two reviewers with expertise in ELSI of genomics (one external to the project, one internal to the project) for quality control. We also received comments from two consortium partners. More details are included at the end of this document in the acknowledgement section.
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Abstract

This deliverable presents a review of the state-of-art of human genomic technologies. It firstly provides a brief description and history of the field indicating the shift from relatively small to large scale analyses of DNA (i.e. genetics to genomics). Subsequently, the field of genomic technologies is further defined and demarcated, including its central concepts (such as DNA, genes, genome, sequencing) as well as a description of current and emerging technologies. These include high throughput sequencing used to **study the genome** and gene editing technologies which are used to **modify the genome**. Next generation sequencing is currently applied in research on human genomes, in clinical care, in direct-to-consumer setting as well as for forensic purposes. Current and potential clinical uses include to facilitate diagnosis, guide treatment, assess predisposition for diseases, screen (sick) newborns, test foetuses and in carrier screening. Meanwhile, gene editing is currently used only in the research context (including clinical trials for somatic gene editing). In the fourth and last section of this deliverable, we present an overview of current and future social and economic impacts of genomic technologies. The estimated economic value of the genomic technologies market(s) and the issue of patents in genomics are presented. Furthermore, current or potential social impacts of genomic technologies are discussed. These are related, among others, to: the possibility of treating or curing more diseases, discrimination on the basis of genetic information, possibility of creating disparities in society, instrumentalization of embryos, and impact on people with disabilities.

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Information in this report that may influence other SIENNA tasks

Linked task	Points of relevance
2.4 Analysis of current and future ethical issues	Applications of the technologies (current and future), Socio-economic impact of the technologies
2.7 Proposal for an ethical framework	Description of applications of the technologies outlines contexts in which the ethical frameworks will be used

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Executive summary

What the reader should know about the general context behind the development of this report

This report was developed in the context of a European Commission (EC) funded SWAFS¹ project called SIENNA, which began in October 2017 (<http://www.sienna-project.eu>). The SWAFS-18-2016² call developed by the EC and categorised as research and innovation action outlined the areas of technologies to be studied and the specific challenges it had identified as important for study. In response to this call, the SIENNA project was developed and ultimately chosen for funding. The partners of the SIENNA project will study the ethical, legal and social issues (ELSI) of three areas of technologies: Human Genomics, AI/Robotics, and Human Enhancement (as dictated by the EC SWAFS call). The report you are currently reading is the first deliverable completed for Work Package (WP) 2 which addresses the ELSI of Human Genomics over the next 36 months of this project. All main authors (HCH, EN, AS) of this report are employed as academic researchers at the Centre for Research Ethics and Bioethics at Uppsala University (Uppsala, Sweden) with main expertise in Genomics and Bioethics (HCH and EN) and in Philosophy and Bioethics (AS). All authors declare having no conflicts of interest regarding the material covered in this report.

Both WP3 (ELSI Human Enhancement) and WP4 (ELSI AI/Robotics) lead by P. Brey (UTwente, NL) and S.K. Nagel (UAachen, De, and UTwente, NL) respectively, have also produced reports with similar aims and outline to this one but addressing their respective technology fields

What is the content of this report?

This report presents a review of the state-of-the-art of genomic technologies used primarily in the context of human genomics.

In Section 1 we provide a brief description and history of the field indicating the shift from relatively small to large scale (genes to whole genomes) on which human DNA has been studied.

In Section 2, the field of genomics (and related technologies) is further defined, and demarcated, including explanations of its central concepts such as DNA, genes, genome, sequencing etc.

In Section 3, the most important current and emergent technologies used in human genomics are described. We focused on two main areas of technologies: 1) high throughput sequencing used to study the genome; and 2) gene editing technologies which modify genomes. We, for example, highlight that high throughput sequencing (and primarily NGS) is currently applied in:

- research on human genomes exploring variation among genomes in given populations, associations between phenotype and genotype, function of genes and regulatory elements in genome, and interactions between genome and environment,

¹ SWAFS = Science with and for Society, <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/opportunities/h2020/calls/h2020-swafs-2018-2020.html#c,topics=callIdentifier/t/H2020-SwafS-2018-2020/1/1/1/default-group&callStatus/t/Forthcoming/1/1/0/default-group&callStatus/t/Open/1/1/0/default-group&callStatus/t/Closed/1/1/0/default-group&+identifier/desc>

² <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/opportunities/h2020/topics/swafs-18-2016.html>

- in clinical care, to facilitate diagnosis, guide treatment, predict predisposition for diseases, screen newborns, test foetuses and in carrier screening,
- in direct-to-consumer setting for testing/screening healthy individuals, children, foetuses
- forensic purposes, using approaches such as predictive phenotyping.

In the future, new applications may be developed such as preimplantation screening of an embryo or monitoring/detecting changes in cell free DNA and RNA in patients in real time using DNA sensors.

Meanwhile, **gene editing** is currently used only in the research context (including clinical trials). Current gene editing research may result in development of clinical applications, both on germline cells (heritable gene editing) and on somatic cells, aiming at curing genetic diseases. Potential applications of gene editing may include:

- germline gene editing – modifying disease-causing genes in DNA of embryos or gametes to prevent disease in future offspring
- somatic gene editing – modifying DNA *in vivo* or *ex vivo* of selected cells (e.g. hemopoietic cells) or organs to correct a disease-causing gene.

In section 4 we present an overview of current and future social and economic impacts of human genomic technologies. Economic values of the genomic technologies markets and the issue of patents in genomics are presented. Furthermore, the current and potential future social impacts of genomic technologies are discussed. In the context of NGS we discussed among others, issues of discrimination on the basis of genetic information, risk of misinterpretation of genetic information, potential psychological harms, and impacts of genetic testing in particular groups, such as newborns, and pregnant women. Meanwhile, in the context of gene editing, we focused our attention on its potential to cure more diseases, possibility of creating disparities in society, instrumentalization of embryos, impact on people with disabilities, and impact of do-it-yourself gene editing kits.

What are the aims and use of this report?

This report, conducted as one of the first tasks of the SIENNA project, and the first task of WP2 on the ELSI of Human Genomics is meant to provide:

- 1- **an overview of the field of genomics**, including technologies and areas of application in society. In this way, it served as a means for us to review our knowledge of and the literature in the field to ensure that we have a full and solid understanding of the relevant scientific realities. It also acts as an educational tool for readers outside of the WP.
- 2- **an exercise to help us (during the following tasks) to find a practical way** of approaching the ELSI study of current and emerging (human) genomic technologies without having to address each and every detailed technology or each and every application while still remaining relevant and meaningful.
- 3- **foundational scientific material needed to properly address the remaining 6 tasks in WP2 and** to which we can keep referring throughout the remaining tasks in the SIENNA project.

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List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
A	Adenine
AI	Artificial intelligence
Bp	Base pair
C	Cytosine
CRISPR-Cas9	Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats Cas-associated nuclease 9
DTC GT	Direct-to-consumer genetic testing
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
EC	European Commission
ELSI	Ethical, legal and social issues/implications
G	Guanine
HGP	Human Genome Project
iPSCs	Induced pluripotent stem cells
IVF	<i>In vitro</i> fertilization
mRNA	Messenger ribonucleic acid
NGS	Next generation sequencing
NHEJ	Non-homologous end joining
NIPT	Non-invasive prenatal testing
NLS	Nuclear localization signal
PAM	Protospacer adjacent motif
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction

PGD/S	Preimplantation genetic diagnosis/screening
PGx	Pharmacogenomics
RNA	Ribonucleic acid
SEIA	Socio-economic impact assessment
sgRNA	Single guide RNA
SIENNA	Stakeholder-informed ethics for new technologies with high socio-economic and human rights impact
SMRT	Single-molecule real-time
STR	Short tandem repeat
T	Thymine
TALEN	Transcription activator-like effector nuclease
ZFN	Zinc finger nuclease

Table 1: List of acronyms/abbreviations

Glossary of terms

Term	Explanation
Adapters	Fragments of external DNA attached to DNA fragments which are prepared for the sequencing reaction; they allow anchoring of the DNA fragments to a surface of a sequencing platform
Allele	A variant of a gene or a DNA locus. A human organism has two alleles of each locus/gene; one allele is inherited from one parent. A pair of alleles of a given gene is called a genotype of that gene
Amniocentesis	The procedure of sampling amniotic fluid, which contains foetal tissues to extract and examine foetal DNA
Carrier testing/screening	Genetic testing or screening aiming to determine if a person carries a gene variant, which may cause a (recessive) disease in their offspring if the same gene variants is present in the second parent
Chorion villus sampling	The procedure of sampling the chorionic villus cells from the placenta for examination; the chorionic villus cells contain the same genetic material as foetal cells
Chromosomal aneuploidy	A type of abnormality in chromosomes number, in which there are too many or too few chromosomes in a cell nucleus
Chromosomal microarray	A technology for detecting copy number changes in a genome: chromosomal duplications or deletions, which may cause disorders
Chromosome	A chromosome is a structural subset of the genome. As a structural unit, it allows genetic material (DNA) to be organized in a (more or less) compact fashion within the cell's nucleus. Proteins such as histones help to organize (e.g. fold) the DNA.
Clonal amplification	The preparation of DNA prior to the sequencing reaction, in which multiple copies of a DNA sequence of interest are generated
CRISPR-Cas9	A site-specific gene editing technology, which is used to introduce precise modifications in genomes
Cytogenetics	The study of chromosomes. Cytogenetic methods (such as karyotyping) are used to diagnose some genetic disorders

Direct-to-consumer genetic testing	An offer of genetic testing in which tests are advertised and/or sold directly to consumers
Dominant disorder	A disorder caused by a dominant mutated gene. Only one copy of such a mutated gene is needed to be affected by such type of a disease. A dominant variant of a gene overrides the effect of a recessive variant of that gene
DNA	A molecule which contains genetic information. It is made of nucleotides, each of which contains a deoxyribose sugar, a phosphate and one of four bases (adenine, guanine, thymine, or cytosine). The order of the nucleotides is a DNA sequence
DNA cloning	Production of copies (typically in bacteria) of a selected fragment of DNA of a given organism
DNA sequencing	The approach or technology of ‘reading’ DNA, that is, obtaining the DNA sequence (order of nucleotides in a given DNA molecule)
Eukaryote	An organism whose cells contain a nucleus
Exome	Protein-coding part of the genome
First generation sequencing	First approaches to DNA sequencing (for example Sanger sequencing) characterized by relatively slow speed of sequencing and very high accuracy when comparing to next generation sequencing technologies
Gene	A gene is a sequence of nucleotides, a fragment of DNA or RNA, which is a functional unit of inheritance. A gene usually contains information about the sequence of amino acids in a protein or polypeptide, however, it may have a function of controlling expression of other genetic material
Gene editing	Approaches of introducing modifications to a genome
Gene therapy	A therapeutic approach involving introducing and/or altering DNA in an organism
Genome	All the DNA of a given organism
Genomics	A field of biology focused on studying genomes. It uses high-throughput technologies, which produce large quantities of data, mainly sequencing data. Traditional genetics focuses on studying a few genes at a time; genomics meanwhile, provides insights into whole genomes thanks to advanced technologies, such as next generation sequencing
Genotype	The genetic makeup of an organism, DNA sequences which determine a given trait
Germline	Concerning the population of cells that may pass on their genetic material to the progeny; examples are: gametes, zygote and embryonic cells
Heterozygous individual	An individual with different alleles of a given gene
Homozygous individual	An individual with two identical alleles of a given gene
Human Genome Project	An international endeavour, originally initiated by the US government. The HGP started in 1990 with the aim to sequence the human genome. Eventually it grew to include an international consortium including researchers in the UK, France, Germany, Japan, China, as well as the USA

Homology directed repair	A mechanism of repairing double strand DNA breaks which uses a homologous (significantly similar) DNA sequence to the one which is repaired
Human induced pluripotent stem cells	The pluripotent stem cells generated from human adult cells, which can give rise to any other cell type in the body (e.g. neurons, heart cells, and liver cells)
<i>In vitro</i> fertilization	The process of fertilizing an egg by sperm conducted outside of an organism, in a laboratory
Karyotyping	A procedure of examining number, size and shape of chromosomes in a sample of cells
Ligation	“Sticking” together end-to-end fragments of DNA
Locus (plural: loci)	A position of a gene or DNA sequence on a chromosome
Microarray (also DNA chip)	A collection of DNA fragments attached to a solid surface used to study a content and expression levels of genomes
Mitochondria	Structures in cells producing “energy-rich” molecules used for various biochemical processes in cells
Mitochondrial replacement	A technique in which the nucleus is transferred from one embryo (or oocyte before fertilization) with mutated DNA in its mitochondria to an embryo (or oocyte before fertilization) with healthy DNA in the mitochondria
Monogenic diseases	Diseases caused by mutation in a single gene
Mosaicism	The occurrence of cells with different genotypes (e.g. where a given gene is modified in some cells, but not in all of them) in one organism
mRNA	Messenger RNA - RNA molecule which carries genetic code from the DNA in the cell’s nucleus to the sites of protein synthesis
Next generation sequencing	Technologies of DNA/RNA sequencing characterized by high-throughput massively parallel approach, whereby millions of DNA strands are sequenced in parallel in a relatively short time period
Non-invasive prenatal testing	A technique allowing for analysis of foetus DNA using blood sample of the mother
Polymerase chain reaction	A technology used in molecular biology to amplify selected fragments of DNA
Phenotype	Observable characteristics of an organisms, such as morphology, physiology, development, resulting from the organism’s genotype and the influence of the environment
Polymorphism	In genetics, an occurrence of more than one DNA sequences in a given locus in a given population
Preimplantation genetic diagnosis and screening	An approach allowing for evaluation of genetic make-up of embryos <i>in vitro</i> before they are implanted in uterus
Prokaryote	A single-celled organism which does not have a nucleus, for example bacteria
Recessive disorder	A disorder caused by two copies of a given recessive gene. Two copies of such a mutated gene are needed to be affected by such type of a disease
Recombinant	Rebuilt with different sources of DNA, e.g. recombinant protein or DNA

Recombinant DNA technology	Technology allowing joining DNA fragments coming from different organisms
Sanger sequencing	The first and widely used technology of DNA sequencing developed by Frederick Sanger and colleagues in 1977. Currently, most recent next generation sequencing technologies are used more commonly, however, Sanger sequencing is still applied, for example to validate next generation sequencing results, due to high accuracy of its results
Sequencing <i>de novo</i>	Sequencing of DNA with no previously known sequence
Single-cell sequencing	An approach in sequencing whereby DNA/RNA of only one cell is sequenced
Somatic	Referring to the cells of the body other than germline cells
Somatic cell nuclear transfer	A technique whereby the nucleus from an adult cell (for example a skin cell) is transferred to an oocyte in which the nucleus was removed
Short tandem repeat (STR; also known as a microsatellite)	A DNA sequence which include a variable number of short (2–6 bp), repeated sequence motifs, where the repeated sequences are directly adjacent to each other
Targeted sequencing	Sequencing of selected genes or fragments of a genome
Third-generation sequencing (long-read sequencing)	An approach in sequencing which does not involve an amplification step to prepare DNA for sequencing and allows for sequencing of much longer fragments of DNA at once (long reads) in real time
Throughput	Amount of DNA that can be sequenced in a single run
Totipotent cells	The cells capable of dividing and developing into a new organism if appropriate maternal conditions are provided
Transcript	RNA sequence produced in the process of transcription from DNA
Trisomy	A presence of an additional, third chromosome in an organism which normally have only two copies of a given chromosome
Whole exome sequencing	An approach where high throughput sequencing is applied in which the protein-coding parts of a genome are sequenced
Whole genome sequencing	An approach where high throughput sequencing is applied in which nearly the entire genome sequence is obtained
Zygote	A fertilized egg, the first developmental stage of an organism

Table 2: Glossary of terms

Section 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction to the deliverable

This report constitutes work for task 2.1 of the SIENNA project (see executive summary for more background context). The domain of technologies for WP2 is human genomics and this deliverable provides a background on the science, as well as on the scope of technologies we will address in the remainder of the project. It also provides a discussion of the most salient social and economic impacts to result from the use of genomic technologies in different areas of application (such as research, clinical practice and forensic genetics).

Genomics is considered the high throughput version of genetics. More traditional or medical genetics typically studies single genes (made up of DNA) one or a few at a time, meanwhile in genomics thousands of genes (that is, huge amounts of DNA) are sequenced and analysed in parallel. In the remainder of this section we provide a short description of the history of genomic technologies. Genomics is currently widely used in all types of research where organisms with DNA are being studied, including prokaryotes (cells without a nucleus, like bacteria) and eukaryotes (organisms which have cells with a nucleus, e.g. plants, animals). All of these areas of application of genomics have significant impact on humans, for example applications in agriculture may impact amount and quality of food produced. Furthermore, animals (such as mice) are used as models to study human diseases. Many more examples of genomic applications in non-human organisms with high relevancy for humans can be described. However, in SIENNA we focus on human genomics, by which we mean specifically applications of genomics that involve human DNA.³

In the next section of this report (Section 2) we provide a detailed demarcation of the field of human genomics, in Section 3 we describe the main technologies currently used in human genomics and possible future technological developments in this field. We also outline the applications of these technologies. In Section 4 we provide a description of socio-economic impact of these technologies.

1.2 Brief history of genomic technologies

1.2.1 Scaling up: from genes to genomes

The origins of genetics, understood as the science of heredity, may be dated back to ancient times when philosophers were reflecting on modes of heritability. The term ‘genetics’, however, was coined only in 1905 by William Bateson, who at some point become familiar with the work of George Mendel recognizing and acknowledging its profound importance⁴. In 1866 George Mendel, Czech monk, published results of his study which investigated the patterns of inheritance of various features of the plants and revealed that the traits are passed on progeny by means of discrete pieces of information, named later genes⁵. The research into genetics in the 20th century brought more insights into the heredity. Solving the structure of DNA in the 1953 by Rosalind Franklin, James Watson and Francis Crick was perhaps the most important achievement of the 20th century genetics.

³ Currently, we exclude the study of ELSI of epigenetics or epigenomics for the sake of pragmatism given resources and timing for this project. However, depending on whether stakeholders refer to this area, we may reconsider this decision.

⁴ Bateson, “William Bateson: A Biologist ahead of His Time.”

⁵ Bateson, *Mendel’s Principles of Heredity*.

Particularly vivid developments in genetics begun in the last quarter of the 20th century. Since then, the field of genetics has advanced rapidly thanks to techniques and technologies allowing the analysis and manipulation of molecules on an increasing scale and at higher pace. To a great extent, the progress of discoveries within genetics and genomics, and subsequent transformation of the medical practice, has been driven by technological developments⁶. Some of the key achievements in genetics were completed thanks to technological advancements, e.g. the structure of DNA (molecule which makes up genes) was discovered thanks to techniques of crystallography⁷. In the 1970s the first genetic technologies⁸ were developed: **recombinant DNA technology** allowing joining DNA fragments coming from different organisms, and **DNA sequencing** - the technology of 'reading' genetic code. In the 1980s another powerful technology was developed - **polymerase chain reaction (PCR)** used to amplify selected fragments of DNA⁹. Recombinant DNA technology and PCR facilitated development of **DNA cloning**, that is, replicating (typically in bacteria) a selected fragment of DNA of a given organism, which allowed study of relatively **small fragments of DNA** and investigation of structure and function of individual genes as well as identification of gene mutations involved in the diseases such as cystic fibrosis and muscular dystrophy¹⁰. Furthermore, DNA cloning was employed for production of recombinant (meaning "rebuilt" and/or rebuilt with different sources of DNA) insulin used as a drug to treat diabetes and other medicinal proteins. In the following years the technology of DNA cloning advanced further, which enabled the study of **larger pieces of DNA**. All the technologies mentioned above, together with technological solutions facilitating analysis of big sets of genetic data were employed in the Human Genome Project (HGP) – an international endeavour which started in 1990 with the aim to sequence (or in simpler words, to obtain a 'readout' of) all human DNA – the genome. The HGP was successfully concluded in 2003 providing a freely accessible high-quality sequence of the entire human genome. The HGP fuelled research endeavours in subsequent years which eventually allowed, for example, the identification of 1,800 genes related to diseases and improvement of diagnosis and treatment of many patients¹¹. Furthermore, the HGP brought a 'revolution' to genetic research initiating new approach in studying DNA - **genomics**, which involves **large-scale studies of genome sequences** using high-throughput technologies and collecting massive amounts of genetic data¹². The capacities of sequencing technologies have rapidly advanced since then, especially in the last two decades allowing for rapid 'reading' of many pieces of the genetic code simultaneously, in other words, sequencing DNA in high-throughput and massively parallel manner. Other high-throughput technologies for examining DNA such as microarrays emerged. The advancements in examining DNA have been used not only in research, but also in

⁶ Galas and McCormack, "An Historical Perspective on Genomic Technologies".

⁷ Klug, "Rosalind Franklin and the Discovery of the Structure of DNA".

⁸ In some instances in this report, the terms 'technique' and 'technology' may be applied interchangeably.

⁹ Saiki et al., "Primer-Directed Enzymatic Amplification of DNA with a Thermostable DNA Polymerase".

¹⁰ Galas and McCormack, "An Historical Perspective on Genomic Technologies".

¹¹ Human Genome Project, National Institutes of Health, <https://report.nih.gov/NIHfactsheets/ViewFactSheet.aspx?csid=45>.

¹² Collins et al., "A Vision for the Future of Genomics Research. A Blueprint for the Genomics Era"; Green et al., "Charting a Course for Genomic Medicine from Base Pairs to Bedside".

clinical practice, among others, to screen and diagnose genetic diseases. Importantly, DNA sequencing is applied also in the reproductive context. For example, non-invasive prenatal testing was developed to examine DNA of a foetus using mother's blood. The high-throughput sequencing technologies as well as technologies for storing and analysing genomic data have also continued to develop. The recent inventions include, for example, sequencing of RNA and a technology of analysing genomes of single cells (see Section 2 and 3 for more details).

1.2.2 Genome modifications in humans

Technologies to genetically modify organisms date back to the 1970s when researchers created first genetically engineered organisms, such as *E.coli* to which a gene from a toad was introduced¹³. The technologies of changing genetic make-up were developed also to (attempt to) treat diseases in humans, these are so called gene therapies. They often employ a viral vector to introduce a functional gene to replace its 'faulty' version. Recently, technologies which can modify a particular gene in an organism more precisely have also been developed. These technologies are now commonly called 'gene editing'. The first gene therapy trials were undertaken in 1990s with limited success and some serious setbacks, such as the death of a patient¹⁴. In the subsequent 20 years, more than 1700 clinical trials employing gene therapy took place and the technology of gene transfer was developed¹⁵. In 2016 the second gene therapy received approval for marketing in Europe and there are others currently undergoing clinical trials¹⁶ (see Section 3.2.2 for details).

Meanwhile, in 2012 a novel gene modifying tool was developed - CRISPR-Cas9 system, allowing for more precise, faster and cheaper modification of genomes¹⁷. This technology can be used to introduce changes in the DNA of somatic cells (that is, not heritable changes) as well as in gametes and embryos in vitro (heritable modifications). In April 2015, in China, CRISPR-Cas9 gene editing technology was used for the first time in human embryos, for research purposes¹⁸. This study sparked controversy, prompting debate and extensive media coverage on this issue, as this research on embryo seemed to be a step forward to clinical application (involving implantation of an embryo in uterus and pregnancy) of this gene manipulation technique. The ability to edit genes changes the paradigm in genomics - from diagnosis to treatment or from reading to *modifying* genomes, raising numerous ethical issues, particularly in relation to potential usage of this technology in human embryos in the clinical context (see Section 4).

In this section, we sought to provide a summary of the history of genetic and genomic technologies with some examples of their impact on clinical practice. It is important, however, to note that the knowledge about heredity and genetic technologies has been transforming not only research and medical practice, but also has been affecting societies and legal systems. The knowledge about

¹³ Morrow et al., "Replication and Transcription of Eukaryotic DNA in Escherichia Coli".

¹⁴ Wirth, Parker, and Ylä-Herttua, "History of Gene Therapy".

¹⁵ Wirth, Parker, and Ylä-Herttua, "History of Gene Therapy".

¹⁶ Senior, "After Glybera's Withdrawal, What's next for Gene Therapy?"

¹⁷ Doudna and Charpentier, "The New Frontier of Genome Engineering with CRISPR-Cas9".

¹⁸ Liang et al., "CRISPR/Cas9-Mediated Gene Editing in Human Triploid Zygotes".

heredity (as well as misconceptions concerning heredity) underlay the eugenics movement, which aimed at eliminating individuals which were considered ‘unfit’ in a society by compulsory euthanasia and sterilizations in Nazi Germany. The currently used genomic technologies also raise many ethical, legal and social aspects, which are discussed to some extent in the subsequent Section 4 of this report and which will be further analysed in subsequent tasks of the SIENNA project.

1.3 Outline of the remainder of the report

In Section 2, the field of genomics (and related technologies) is further defined, and demarcated, including explanations of its central concepts such as DNA, genes, genome, sequencing. Indeed, as an introductory section, this has been written in as easy language as possible in order to address as wide range of types of readers.

In Section 3, the most important current and emergent technologies used in human genomics are described. We focused on two main areas of technologies: 1) high throughput sequencing used to study the genome; and 2) gene editing technologies which modify genomes. Given the technical nature of the topic, the language in this section while still aiming to be educational, may not be considered quite as “simple” as that in section 2.

In Section 4, we present an overview of current and future social and economic impacts of human genomic technologies.

Section 2 Defining the Field

In section 2, we present key aspects and concepts needed to better understand the field of human genomics and in order to situate the emerging technologies in the field (which are described in section 3). The focus of this deliverable, and indeed, of the entire Genomics Work Package in SIENNA is *human* genomics and not genomics as applied to other areas (including, for example, to agriculture or to farm animals).

2.1. Demarcation and definition of the field: Genome, Genomics and Genomic technologies

2.1.1 What is a genome?

The **genome** corresponds to **the entire genetic material of any living organism**. It contains all hereditary instructions for building and maintaining an organism and is the main vehicle used to pass information on to the next generation. Each species has its own distinctive genome and within a species, each individual has their own unique genome. The difference is a matter of degree: a person's genome is unique in the sense that it is different from that of every other human, but the differences between their genome and the genome of another human are much smaller than the genome differences between humans and other species.

The genome is divided into chromosomes. Chromosomes contain genes and genes are made of DNA. Chromosomes are tiny packages that contain one DNA molecule and its associated proteins.

Figure 1: Structure of a chromosome. This image was created by the NHS HEE Genomics Education Programme. <https://www.flickr.com/photos/genomicseducation/13062250965/> Shared under Attribution 2.0 Generic (CC BY 2.0) Creative Commons License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/2.0/>).

In humans, each cell normally contains 23 pairs of **chromosomes**, for a total of 46. Twenty-two of these pairs, called autosomes, look the same (i.e. have the same string of genes) in both males and

females. The 23rd pair, the sex chromosomes, differs between males and females. Females have two copies of the X chromosome, while males have one X and one Y chromosome.

Genes are segments of chromosomes that are strung together in such a way that the sequence of DNA they carry determines how living organisms inherit their various features. For example, offspring usually look similar to each of their parents because they have inherited some of each of their parents' genes. Normally, every person carries two variations of every gene, one inherited from their mother, the other inherited from their father. Genes are inherited as units, with two parents dividing out copies of their genes to their offspring. This process can be compared with mixing two hands of cards, shuffling them, and then dealing them out again. The effects of this mixing depend on the types of the gene. As a fictional and simplified example (since hair colour, is in truth, mediated by many different genes): if the father has two copies of a gene for red hair, and the mother has two copies for brown hair, all their children get the two alleles that give different instructions, one for red hair and one for brown. The hair colour of these children depends on how these genes “work” relative to each other. If one gene dominates the instructions from another, it is called the *dominant* gene¹⁹, and the gene that is “overridden” is called the *recessive* gene. In the case of a daughter with genes for both red and brown hair, if the gene for brown is dominant then, she will end up with brown hair. Many traits, including hair colour, are inherited in a more complicated way than the example above. This can happen when there are several genes involved, each contributing a small part to the end result.

As the example above suggests, genes carry information that is particular to a characteristic of a person's body. It may carry information about things we can see – such as hair colour or the shape of one's nose – but also about things we cannot see, such as for instance how well our bodies can fight disease. Whilst the two copies of the genes we inherited from our mother and our father may each contain information about the same characteristic – hair colour for instance – the information they carry is different – in our example, the father's gene carried information about red hair, and the mother's gene carried information about brown hair. We call these different kinds of information ‘alleles’. Alleles are alternative forms of the same gene.

Before the completion of the Human Genome Project, many scientists were expecting to find more genes in our genome than in any other animal or plant (upwards of 100 000 genes). However, the most recent estimates suggest that humans only have around 19 000 genes. Scientists also discovered that large parts of our genome are made up of DNA that does not code for genes.

DNA is the genetic material that is used by living cells to make proteins from amino acids. DNA is made up of four building blocks called nucleotides (adenine, cytosine, guanine, and thymine – abbreviated as A, C, G, and T). There are two strings of nucleotides coiled around one another in each chromosome. When joined together, these strings form a double helix. There are about 3.2 billion nucleotide pairs in our human genome. Within the order of the nucleotides lies the genetic information which will dictate which amino acids will be included in a protein and in which order. The order of these letters thus form the genetic code – that is similar to how the order of letters on a page of text carries information or has a meaning.

¹⁹ Technically, what we call the dominant allele, is in fact an allele, the expression of which, can be seen to follow what we call «a dominant inheritance» pattern. And recessive alleles, allow for expression of the phenotype which follows a «recessive inheritance pattern».

The information in DNA is held in the sequence of the repeating units (As, Cs, Gs, Ts) along the DNA chain. When a cell “reads” a gene, the DNA sequence is copied into a very similar molecule called RNA. The RNA copy made from a gene is then fed through a structure called a ribosome, which translates the sequence of nucleotides in the RNA into the correct sequence of amino acids and joins these amino acids together to make a complete protein chain. And then, the new protein can fold up into its (in)active form, join up with other proteins if needed, and take up the “job” or activity it has to do in the cell.

Chromosome	A chromosome is a structural subset of the genome. As a structural unit, it allows genetic material (DNA) to be organized in a (more or less) compact fashion within the cell’s nucleus. Proteins such as histones help to organize (e.g. fold) the DNA.
Gene	A gene is a sequence of nucleotides, a fragment of DNA or RNA, which is a functional unit of inheritance. A gene usually contains information about the sequence of amino acids in a protein or polypeptide, however, it may have a function of controlling expression of other genetic material.
Allele	An allele is a variant of a gene or a DNA locus. A human organism has two alleles of each locus/gene; one allele is inherited from one parent. A pair of alleles of a given gene is called a genotype of that gene.
Gene expression and regulation of gene expression	Gene expression is the process by which information from a gene is used to synthesise a functional gene product, for example a protein, or RNA molecule. Gene expression includes a few steps, such as transcription and translation, which are controlled by regulatory mechanisms. Regulation of gene expression includes a wide range of mechanisms that are used by cells to increase or decrease the production of specific gene products (protein or RNA).
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) – a molecule which contains genetic information. It is made of nucleotides, each of which contains a deoxyribose sugar, a phosphate and one of four bases (adenine, guanine, thymine, or cytosine). The order of the nucleotides is a DNA sequence.
Mitochondrial DNA	Mitochondrial (mt) DNA refers to a small portion of the DNA that is not located in the cell nucleus but in cellular organelles called mitochondria. Mitochondria have a function of generating energy for cells in the form of adenosine triphosphate.
RNA	Ribonucleic acid (RNA) is a molecule, which, like DNA, is assembled as a chain of nucleotides. There are several types of RNA, which have different functions: mRNA - messenger RNA which is an intermediate element in gene expression; tRNA (transfer RNA) and rRNA (ribosomal RNA) take part in translation (i.e. process of protein synthesis in cells).
DNA sequence	A DNA sequence is an order of nucleotides in a DNA molecule; each of nucleotides contains one of four bases: adenine, guanine, thymine, or cytosine.

	DNA sequence defines function of a given DNA molecule, e.g. expression of proteins and RNA molecules, DNA regulatory function. DNA sequencing aims to determine DNA sequence which can be further studied to understand its function.
Genomic variation	Genomic variation refers to differences in the sequences of DNA among individuals. Mutations (that is, spontaneous or induced changes in DNA) are sources of genomic variation.

Table 3: Definitions of basic biological terms in genomics

2.1.2 Why deciphering the human genome?

Through the sequencing of a genome, we can reach a greater understanding of the structure, function, and evolution of our bodies, including how we respond to disease and environmental challenges. While the deciphering of a model organisms’ genome, whether animal or plant, presents its own benefits and challenges, the Human Genome Project and subsequent projects to understand human variation have been presented as exceptional scientific endeavours. From a scientific (or primarily academic) point of view, this may be explained by the great variety of scientific applications that are served by the (greater) knowledge of the human genome:

- **In molecular anthropology**, the comparison of DNA sequences in different populations allows for an evaluation of the closeness of relationships between populations (or within populations), in order to better understand and represent human diversity from a biological perspective.
- **In molecular biology**, sequencing allows researchers to study genomic variability and thus to identify changes in genes, to establish potential associations between the sequence and diseases and phenotypes, and to examine how drugs may interact differently according to genomic variability.
- **In evolutionary biology**, since DNA informs about the transmission from one generation to another, DNA sequencing allows studying how different organisms are related and how they evolved.
- **In medicine**, medical doctors sequence genes, parts of or full genomes from patients to determine a molecular diagnosis for a monogenic condition (i.e. identify the underlying genetic cause/variant for the disease phenotype) or to study complex diseases. Sequencing may also be used to find risk alleles, which could increase a person’s risk of developing a disease if there is risk of genetic diseases.
- **In forensics**²⁰, DNA profiling methods using sequencing are used for paternity testing and forensic identification.

2.1.3 Genomics and Genetics

Genetics is generally described as the study of heredity²¹ and traditionally it involved the study of one or a few genes at a time. Genomics is defined as the study of multiple genes and their functions, and

²⁰ We refer to forensics herein as the application of science to criminal and civil laws for security purposes.

²¹ WHO, *Genomics and World Health: Report of the Advisory Committee on Health Research*.

related techniques²². The main difference between genomics and genetics is that genetics scrutinizes the functioning and composition of a single gene whereas genomics studies all genes and their inter-relationships in order to identify their combined influence on the growth and development of the organism.

In practice, genetics and genomics are overlapping disciplines and some will use the words genetic and genomic interchangeably. For instance, genetic and genomic tests may in the end provide the same type of genetic information through a different type of process: one can thus distinguish between a genetic or a genomic test, based on the amount of DNA to be processed at a time. During genetic testing, researchers investigate specific bits of DNA with a known function. Examples of (mono)genetic conditions for which such testing is routinely conducted include cystic fibrosis, hemophilia, Huntington's disease, phenylketonuria (PKU), sickle-cell disease and Down syndrome. During genomic testing, researchers are not targeting a specific fragments of DNA but exploring broader regions so as to address heterogeneous conditions, i.e. conditions that are contributed to by several genes or alleles and/or complex diseases, i.e. diseases caused by a combination of genetic, environmental and lifestyle factors (for example, asthma, diabetes, epilepsy, hypertension and schizophrenia).

The current meaning of '**genomics**' was first introduced by McKusick and Ruddle in their inaugural editorial for the new journal *Genomics* in 1987²³. Referring to 'genomics' as "a new name, a new discipline, a new journal", this neologism was meant to distinguish the emerging approaches of large-scale mapping and DNA sequencing efforts from molecular studies of one or a few genes. Although the specificity of genomics as a clear-cut discipline has largely been debated since²⁴, the term has come to describe a growing field of molecular biology associated with **large-scale DNA analysis** to decipher **DNA structure and function** and **intensive use of new technologies**. A particularity of the field is the **extensive use of computation** required for DNA sequencing interpretation and calculation of metrics of DNA variation. A second characteristic is the **enormous amount of data generated** in genomics research and clinical practice. Along with this, there has been an increasing need for experts in bioinformatics to be part of the genomics field, an expertise that was not needed (or even well known) in the more traditional context of genetic testing.

The novelty and the use of highly innovative technologies in genomics inscribe the discipline in a specific dynamic of expectations, making it prone to create hope, hype and disappointments²⁵. In the way the future of genomic technologies is envisioned, there is thus strong accountability to cultivate so as to manage the political economy of biotechnological expectations related to the field.

2.1.4 What are genomic technologies?

Genomic technologies can simply be defined as the different entities – involving various technical processes, methods and devices – developed **to read, analyze and manipulate genomic information**. This field thus relates to the various technologies developed so as to process previously unseen

²² Ibid.

²³ Gupta and Musunuru, "Expanding the Genetic Editing Tool Kit: ZFNs, TALENs, and CRISPR-Cas9".

²⁴ Patrick, Eric, and Zhang, "Development and Applications of CRISPR-Cas9 for Genome Engineering".

²⁵ Gottweis, "Governing Genomics in the 21st Century: Between Risk and Uncertainty."; Hilgartner, "Selective Flows of Knowledge in Technoscientific Interaction: Information Control in Genome Research"; Brown, "Hope against Hype--Accountability in Biopasts, Presents and Futures".

amount of DNA. However, this apparent simplicity should hide neither the variety of settings where genomic technologies may be used - making it a **plural technological field** – nor the plethora of techniques, methods and processes that can be referred to as ‘genomic technologies’. We present hereafter, first, the main settings of applications of genomic technologies and second, how this technological field can be divided into several subfields, depending on their technological purpose.

Genomics as a plural technological field

The **field of human genomic technologies** encompasses all techniques, processes and methods that may be of use to both explore and transform the human genome in the **various settings** in which these activities might be of interest. Genomic technologies may refer to the same or similar technical processes, methods and devices used in those settings – including clinical, research, forensic, commercial or translational settings:

- **Medical technologies:** the collection of techniques, processes and methods concerned with the performance of laboratory genomic analyses used in the diagnosis, the treatment of disease and the maintenance of health.
- **Genomic technologies designed for research:** the collection of techniques, processes and methods designed to investigate biological questions (including research on diseases, or population structure) in the course of scientific investigation (and/or to improve current equipment and methods).
- At a **translational stage**, genomic technologies refer to the storage, analytic and interpretive methods developed to allow for genomic research to be transformed into prevention, diagnosis and therapies.
- **DNA forensic technologies:** the collection of techniques, processes and methods used to determine DNA profiling to be presented as part of police or legal proceedings
- **Commercial genomic technologies:** the collection of techniques, processes and methods used to develop the products (instruments, agents, software, sequencers) needed in genomic analysis; or to propose genetic tests directly addressed to consumers.

A variety of subfields

The field of human genomic technology is a broad area that combines engineering and genomic science to solve biological or medical problems; it can also be used in the accomplishment of other objectives, such as criminal investigations or to be developed in the production of goods for commercial use. Regardless of the variety of its contexts of usage, this general field may also be broken down into smaller (possibly overlapping) sub-fields of activity according to the focus, methods and techniques the subfield requires.

- **Biobanking:** this subfield concerns all organizational and technological activities connected to the creation and maintenance of repositories of human biological material and related data. They can be defined as “structured resources that can be used for the purpose of genetic research (among others) and which include: (i) human biological materials and/or information generated from the analysis of the same; and (ii) extensive associated information”²⁶.
- **Genomic databases:** this sub-field refers to the collections of genomic data that are

²⁶ Lidz and Appelbaum, “The Therapeutic Misconception: Problems and Solutions”.

developed in machine-readable forms so as to be manipulated by software. Among them, **curated databases** may be “less complete than primary databases but they have less redundancy and the added value of scientific annotation”²⁷ which makes a biologically significant sequence easier to find and thus of greater value. Examples of these curated databases, include dbSNP, and DECIPHER.

- **DNA profiling technologies:** this subfield refers to the techniques and methods used to determine an individual's or group's specific DNA characteristics (his/its DNA profile) so as to test the likelihood that some given genetic material came from a particular individual or group. These technologies involve kits to collect DNA samples, various methods of analysis (Restriction fragment length polymorphism analysis, Polymerase Chain Reaction analysis, Short Tandem Repeat analysis, DNA family relationship analysis, Y-chromosome analysis, mitochondrial analysis) and DNA databases (used notably in the forensic context to evaluate the likelihood of a match between the profile of the suspect and the crime evidence against a reference population).
- **Genome sequencing technologies / Sequencers:** given that “sequencing” consists in figuring out the **order of DNA nucleotides** in a genome, this subfield concerns the techniques used to collect genetic material and, if necessary, amplify material for the analysis (an *in vitro* cloning step is usually needed **to amplify DNA molecules**, because molecular detection methods are not sensitive enough for single molecule sequencing), and all methods used to determine the order of the four bases.

For large-scale sequencing (which includes very long DNA pieces or a very large number of short sequences) as it is the case for **whole genome sequencing**, technologies include the techniques used to cut up the genome into smaller pieces, sequence these pieces, and then reassemble them in the correct order on the basis of their overlapping regions (the most popular method is called Shotgun sequencing).

Sequencing methods have greatly evolved, from the **manual** approaches used in the 1970's and 1980's and 90's (Maxam-Gibert sequencing and Sanger sequencing) to the **automated** versions developed thereafter (e.g. illumine dye sequencing, pyrosequencing, SMRT sequencing etc.). The methods developed in the early 2000's, called '**next generation**' or '**second generation**' technologies have been implemented in commercial **DNA sequencers**. Sequencers can be considered optical instruments: they analyze light signals originating from fluorescent chemicals which stain differently As, Cs, Gs and Ts, and then report their translation of the colors observed, in a text string called a 'read'. In order to accelerate this process and to low down its cost, high **throughput technologies** have been developed, that parallelize the sequencing process.

A **third generation of sequencers** is now being introduced that does not require DNA amplification, thus speeding up the process and reducing errors. The first approach, called Single-molecule real-time (SMRT), allows sequencing data to be produced by light (captured by a camera) emitted when a nucleotide is added to its complementary DNA strand by enzymes containing fluorescent dyes²⁸. The second approach, called nanopore sequencing,

²⁷ Harisha, *Fundamentals of Bioinformatics*.

decodes DNA directly as the molecule is drawn through a membrane. Changes in electric current indicate which one of the 4 bases is successively present²⁹.

- **Genomic engineering:** this subfield refers to the application of engineering design and principles to target specific modification of the genome. It involves laboratory methods, such as ‘recombinant DNA’, ‘gene targeting’, or ‘**genome editing**’ to add, delete or otherwise change an organism’s DNA.
- **Genome informatics or bioinformatics:** this sub-field is concerned with the development of computational and statistical techniques for the management and the manipulation of genomic data so as to derive biological information from genome variants or sequences. This sub-field encompasses all computer-based techniques to analyze DNA sequence information – including data mining, knowledge extraction, data pattern processing, algorithm development and software engineering.

2.2 Tensions in the field

2.2.1 Testing and screening

A **genetic test or a genetic assay** is used to **provide information** about a person’s DNA. The first genetic tests were developed from the 1950s onwards for genetic conditions such as Down syndrome, cystic fibrosis, and Duchenne muscular dystrophy. Chromosomal genetic testing was used to analyze whole chromosomes or long lengths of DNA to see if there are large genetic changes, such as an extra copy of a chromosome or part of a chromosome, which causes a genetic condition. Based on the same principle but occurring at a finer resolution, molecular genetic tests (or gene tests) have afterwards been developed to study single genes or short lengths of DNA to identify mutations that could lead to a genetic disorder.

Regardless of which method is used, genetic testing primarily serves **to make the diagnosis of a genetic condition**: it is used to confirm or rule out a suspected genetic condition. It can also be used to help determine a person’s chance of developing or passing on a genetic disorder. Genetic testing should always be **voluntary**. As genetic testing holds **benefits** but also bears **limitations** and **risks**, the decision to be tested is personal and complex. A geneticist or genetic counselor can help by providing information about the pros and cons of the test and discussing the social and emotional aspects of testing in order to support informed decisions making.

Based on the same technologies and methods, **screening** however differs in terms of usage, as it does not target individuals but **populations**. Genetic screening is *“a type of public health program that is systematically offered to a specified population of asymptomatic individuals with the aim of providing those identified as high risk with prevention, early treatment, or reproductive options”*³⁰. Prenatal and newborn screening programs are for example proposed in order to interrupt at-risk pregnancies or so that early interventions and treatments could be administered at the newborn stage when symptoms may be difficult to observe. **Effectiveness** and **feasibility** of the tests proposed for screening have to be demonstrated, as well as their **acceptability** from the perspective of individuals and families, but also for target populations and society as a whole – as those wide

³⁰ “National Institutes of Health Fact Sheets. Human Genome Project (2017)”.

medical interventions play a normative role in our collective views towards ‘**difference**’³¹. The contexts of genetic screening and genetic testing raise very similar as well as distinct ethical, legal and social issues. For example, obtaining consent for a public health programs such as newborn screening has been considered very differently from informed consent in testing.

2.2.2 Diagnosis and treatment

The complexity of genetic diagnosis, and its relation with treatment

In clinical practice, the primary functions of genetic testing (and screening) are (i) to ultimately identify DNA variants that are causal or increase the risk of developing a genetic disorder or (ii) to serve a molecular diagnosis, that can be defined as the judgment made by medical authorities about an illness or a problem involving a genetic cause, mainly based on an examination of the genetic makeup of a person, at the level of the chromosomes or genes. Genetic or molecular diagnoses, however, do not always entirely depend on karyotype or DNA analysis: different approaches “including the physical examination, family history, routine hematology, chemistry or pathology studies, and radiological and electrophysiological examinations” may lead to a genetic diagnosis as well³². Usually, however, when a genetic disease is suspected, a molecular genetic test is then conducted to confirm this diagnosis.

Diagnosis is an important step of healthcare as it provides routes for treatments, that it to say: i) adapted care and management of a patient; and possibly ii) therapy to combat, ameliorate or prevent a genetic disorder. The identification of the precise cause for an illness or problem indeed allows for medical, and more generally, institutional, care (leading to adapted schooling, adapted work conditions, government support etc.).

In best-case scenarios, a diagnosis will allow for treatment or prevention. This was, for example, the case when newborns were screened for PKU (phenylketonuria), a genetic disorder affecting the metabolism so that amino acid builds up in the blood and causing mental retardation. However, if the disorder is detected early enough, strict dietary treatment preserves brain function. In this case, the testing procedure is effective and the disease to be diagnosed is treatable, hence its implementation in screening programs.

For other diseases, with no treatment or prevention, other forms of screening programs have however been considered. This is the case for carrier screening for Tay-Sachs disease, which is particularly present in the Jewish community, where children die in the first months or years after birth due to, their nervous systems shutting down. Many programs started to test young people for several recessive genetic disorders often encountered in the Jewish population, and to help determine potential marital compatibility for couples by identifying carriers for the same diseases. The process is anonymous, using numbers to identify people tested, and carriers are not told what they carry, they are however told before (deciding to) marriage whether their descent would be at risk.

Predictive testing for Huntington disease is more specialized, reserved for people with a family history of this disorder, which typically begins near age 40 and causes uncontrollable movements and

³¹ Green et al., “Charting a Course for Genomic Medicine from Base Pairs to Bedside”; Collins et al., “A Vision for the Future of Genomics Research”.

³² Wirth, Parker, and Ylä-Herttua, “History of Gene Therapy”.

cognitive and behavioral deterioration For this disorder, the more copies of a telltale DNA base triplet in the implicated gene, the earlier, faster, and/or more severe the symptoms. In contrast with the tests mentioned earlier, results for the tests of BRCA1 and BRCA2 are more complicated to interpret, especially as BRCA1 and 2 account for only a small percentage of breast cancer cases. A mutation carries different risks of actually developing cancer in different populations, and a result could be of uncertain clinical significance (as a variation in the DNA sequence tested may or may not cause cancer). There are thus questions as to how decisive actions such as prophylactic mastectomy may be supported by testing results.

In clinical practice, there is thus no unique way of viewing the relation between genetic diagnosis and treatment as this is highly variable, and highly dependent on the type of disorder considered and whether therapies are available or not.

Pharmacogenomics

Pharmacogenomics is the study of how genes affect a person's response to drugs. Genetic testing may help to choose a certain course of care and to adjust therapies with precision. This knowledge is used to predict whether a medication will be effective for a particular person and to help prevent adverse drug reactions. In the case of breast cancer, for instance, the activity and interaction of certain genes in the tumor influences its propensity to grow and spread. In some cases, genomic tests can predict the aggressiveness of the tumor and whether the patient will or will not benefit from certain chemotherapy. This "personalized" information, may be key to decide for which therapy to opt in a course of treatment.

Gene therapy and Genome editing

To date, most of clinical genetic activities have been based on studying genes, and more recently genomes in order to provide a diagnosis. With tools like CRISPR Cas9, which allows for more efficient ways to modify genes or genomes, genetics or genomics could also be used as treatment.

Gene therapy (aka, **genome therapy**, **genetic engineering**) encompasses a large scope of techniques, which are still mostly experimental. They aim to use genetic material or genetic tools to treat or cure diseases (usually for diseases that have no other cures – whether inherited disorders or not, some types of cancer or certain viral infections). The goal is to introduce nucleic acid into a patient's cells to treat or prevent disease instead of using drugs or surgery. The different approaches to gene therapy include:

- "Replacing a mutated gene that causes disease with a healthy copy of the gene.
- Inactivating a mutated gene that is functioning improperly.
- Introducing a new gene into the body to help fight a disease" (cf. Your Guide to Understanding Genetic Conditions", NIH – US National Library of Medicine, <https://ghr.nlm.nih.gov/primer/therapy/genetherapy>).

Genome editing (aka **gene editing**) is a term used only in recent years, which refers to genetic engineering using a particular group of tools or group of molecular technologies that enable an intervention directly on the genome in order to change, add or remove specific locations on the DNA sequence. This can be used to "correct" variants that would otherwise cause a genetic disorder; hence it can also be considered a type of gene therapy. Among the different methods developed, CRISPR-Cas9 (Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats and CRISPR-associated protein 9) is currently the fastest, cheapest and most accurate. While genome editing is still at the

research stage, should it prove efficient and safe, scientists suggest that it might allow for prevention and treatment of several diseases: monogenetic disorders of course but also cancer, heart disease, mental illness and human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection^{33 34}. Given that gene editing can be used in both somatic cells and germ line cells, a lot of ethical, legal and social issues accompany the latter proposal. (More is discussed about this in section 4.)

Blur between research and clinic

Genomic research can be defined as the process to derive meaningful knowledge from the DNA sequence. **Clinical research** may take place (at least in part) in clinics and involve patients but its aim is to collect evidence (to determine the analytic validity, clinical validity, utility of a test, or in other word, the safety and effectiveness of a diagnostic product or of a treatment) and not to treat patients. **Clinical genetics** on the contrary is a medical specialty that proposes **genetic testing** (diagnosis) and **genetics counseling** (support for diagnosis) to individuals and families with, or at risk of, genetic disorders.

The main differences between clinical genetic testing and research testing are the purpose of the test and who receives the results, the legal framework, and responsibility of stakeholders. Researchers intend to find unknown genes or more information on the workings of known genes, to learn how genes work and interact within the genome and with the environment, to develop new tests; whereas clinicians intend to find out about an inherited disorder in order to make decisions about treatment and management (care and therapies) and/or reproductive issues. Research participants usually do not get individual results, while patient usually do. Physicians have a duty of care towards their patients, (genomic) researchers do not per se; one could argue, however that both have a duty to rescue.

The **clinical** and **research setting** should, therefore, not be confused as they do not have the same finalities and do not entail the same system of obligations towards patients and research participants. The term “*therapeutic misconception*” has even been created to label situations when a research subject fails to appreciate “*the distinction between the imperatives of clinical research and of ordinary treatment*”³⁵.

However, in genetics, the status of patients, particularly those affected with rare disorders, may easily shift to research participant as medical doctors include their profile in research databases to look for genotype-phenotype associations, which would allow for an identification of the patient’s disorder. Boundaries between research and clinics tend also to blur because of the transfer of new technologies of genetic testing into clinics. Sequencing technologies, developed in the context of genome research, have become cheaper and more efficient so that they are now accessible to hospital laboratories and may be used to screen for disease risk, to assess a patient’s pharmacogenomics profile or to explore the genetic variation underlying rare disorders. But this technological transfer raises questions as to the kind of practices to be developed in clinics and its impact on both research and clinics.

The availability of genomic technologies in clinics may indeed create “*a pressure on the research enterprise to provide individualized care more typical of the clinic setting because it is uniquely*

³³ Ibid.

³⁴ Senior, “After Glybera’s Withdrawal, What’s next for Gene Therapy?”

³⁵ Doudna and Charpentier, “The New Frontier of Genome Engineering with CRISPR-Cas9”.

*accessible in research. Such blurring can have lasting implications, both by expanding obligations imposed on researchers, but also by challenging long-held ethical views*³⁶. On the clinical side, the interpretation of analytical results produced by genomic technologies “in terms of their clinical relevance and the predicted health status poses a challenge to both laboratory and clinical geneticists, due to the wealth and complexity of the information obtained”³⁷. Indeed, as more data is generated and gathered through genomic sequencing, there does seem to be a “data imperative” where it is being considered a “duty” for patients to donate their data to research, and for researchers to use this data, potentially undermining free choice on the one hand, and good research on the other.

³⁶ Liang et al., “CRISPR/Cas9-Mediated Gene Editing in Human Triprounuclear Zygotes”.

³⁷ Rout, Mishra, and Sankar Prasad Mishra, “Mapping of Genes Using Cloud Technologies”.

Section 3 Description of genomic technologies and their applications

The aim of this section is to provide a description of technologies used in the field of human genomics, including the approaches they enable, their major applications and anticipated future developments. Genomic technologies may be classified according to various criteria, e.g. area of application (research, clinic), purpose, scale of use, and market value. Herein we distinguish categories of technologies which are used to 1) explore the human genome and 2) modify the human genome. We also describe briefly technologies which involve DNA in some way, however, which would be classified as molecular biology technologies rather than genomic technologies. We also outline genomic technologies which are not used for analysis/modification of human genome, but their applications are relevant in the context of human healthcare, for example sequencing of bacterial DNA (Section 3.3). This section also addresses the areas specified in the SWAFs work programme call with relation to the field of genomics:

- Genetic testing and screening (Section 3.1.2)
- Pharmacogenomics (Section 3.1.2)
- Genetic patents, (Section 4.2.1)
- Genetic databanks (Section 3.1.2)

3.1 Technologies used to explore genomes

As discussed in section 1 (history of human genomics technologies), after completion of the Human Genome Project in 2003, genetics underwent a shift from studying fewer variants or smaller areas to studying whole genomes – genomics. This change of paradigm took place thanks to the development of, among others, efficient technologies for sequencing (reading) genomes, and a drop in price of these technologies. Sequencing of the first human genome using **Sanger sequencing**³⁸ (also called **first-generation sequencing**) completed in 2003 took 13 years and cost 2.7 billion of U.S. dollars³⁹. Sanger sequencing, although precise, is a laborious and low-throughput technique⁴⁰. It is still used in research and clinics to obtain or confirm sequences of regions which cannot be sequenced with adequate accuracy using more recent sequencing technologies⁴¹. In the last decade, new technologies emerged allowing for high-throughput and massively parallel sequencing, that is rapid ‘reading’ of many DNA or RNA fragments simultaneously. Thanks to these new generation sequencing (NGS) technologies, a whole human genome can be sequenced within just a few weeks, at a cost below 1000 US dollars (the timing and cost may not include complete interpretation), which may be reduced further⁴². Due to the increased availability, NGS technologies are increasingly used in human genomics, both in the clinic and research settings, as well as in direct-to-consumer setting (i.e. where tests are advertised and/or sold directly to consumers, and not to healthcare

³⁸ From name of its inventor, Frederick Sanger, who sequenced the first the whole genome of an organism, bacteriophage. Sanger et al., “Nucleotide Sequence of Bacteriophage Phi X174 DNA.”

³⁹ National Human Genome Research Institute. The Human Genome Project Completion: Frequently Asked Questions, <https://www.genome.gov/11006943/human>

⁴⁰ Nelan, Hayward, and Jones, “The Growth of Molecular Diagnostics: Stratified Medicine Programme, the 100,000 Genomes Project and the Future”.

⁴¹ Rehm et al., “ACMG Clinical Laboratory Standards for next-Generation Sequencing.”

⁴² Illumina Promises To Sequence Human Genome For \$100 -- But Not Quite Yet, <https://www.forbes.com/sites/matthewherper/2017/01/09/illumina-promises-to-sequence-human-genome-for-100-but-not-quite-yet/#350a8dca386d>.

professionals) (see Section 3.1.2 for details). In this section we will focus on NGS technologies, given their current and potentially growing impact on research and clinical care as well as time limitations. However, NGS technology is not the only technology allowing us to explore the human genome. Table 4 provides a summary of other technologies providing insights into the human genome; we refer to some of them in the remainder of this report.

Technology	Examples of applications
DNA sequencing	clinic e.g. for diagnosis, research, forensics (see the remainder of this section for detailed descriptions)
Microarrays	used to study content and expression levels of genomes in research and clinical care
Cytogenetics techniques	used to study chromosomal structure in research and clinical care, for example to reveal chromosomal abnormalities
Polymerase chain reaction	detects presence of given DNA sequences and allows for amplification of specific regions of DNA, used in research, clinical care and forensics

Table 4: List of selected technologies used to study (as opposed to transform) genomes

3.1.1 Description of sequencing technologies

Currently a variety of technologies are available in the fast-changing market of DNA sequencing, however, the last decade has been monopolised by next generation sequencing (NGS) technologies (called also second-generation sequencing technologies). The main manufacturers (which have been developing and offering NGS in 2016 include Illumina, Inc. (U.S.), Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc. (U.S.), and Pacific Biosciences of California, Inc. (U.S.)⁴³. Characteristics of selected NGS approaches is summarised in Table 5. The table and descriptions below do not detail all available technologies, but rather focus on the most commonly used and/or discussed approaches and their principles. It is important to keep in mind that landscape of NGS technologies is dynamically evolving. As shown in Table 5, some sequencers are not sold any longer; meanwhile some companies have been developing novel platforms for sequencing. Of note, sequencing technologies have been developed (mostly) by companies (and not by publicly funded research); some of the providers offer not only sequencing platforms, but also components needed to prepare samples and DNA, components for sequencing, as well as software for data analysis as is the case of the GeneReader NGS system⁴⁴.

Next generations sequencing technologies involve a step of DNA library preparation, called clonal amplification. This step includes initial cleavage of DNA to fragments of equal length, amplification of the fragments and attachment of fragments to external DNA (adapters). Adapters allow anchoring of the DNA fragments to a surface of a sequencing platform (e.g. Illumina) or beads (e.g. Ion Torrent), after which a sequencing reaction takes place. DNA fragmentation and amplification are necessary as one of the limitations of many sequencing approaches is the read length, that is length of DNA

⁴³ NGS technologies market, <http://marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/next-generation-sequencing-ngs-technologies-market-546.html>.

⁴⁴ GeneReader Platform, <https://www.qiagen.com/us/products/ngs/mdx-ngs-generader/library-preparation/qiagen-generader-platform/>.

fragments which can be sequenced at once (35-300 base pairs (bps) per read)⁴⁵. Average read length is much shorter than the length of the sequences which are analysed in NGS (for example, human genome has around 3Gbps), therefore the DNA has to be fragmented and amplified prior to sequencing. The obtained fragments of a sequence are assembled in bioinformatic analysis. Sequencing reactions may be based on ligation (“sticking” together end-to-end) or synthesis (sequential building) of molecules which emit specific signals indicating presence of one of the following bases: adenine (A), thymine (T), cytosine (C) or guanine (G). Signals, for example light of a given wave length or change in pH (Ion Torrent system) are detected by sensors (such as optical sensors or solid state – where electrical signals take through solid pieces a of semi-conductor) and recorded. The signals are converted into data – sequence data that is made up of the order of the four bases (A, T, C, and G) in a studied DNA strand.

Unlike sequencing approaches involving clonal amplification step, **single-molecule sequencing**⁴⁶, reads the sequence directly from individual strands of DNA. This approach, called by some **third-generation sequencing**, allows for: i) sequencing of much longer fragments of DNA at once (long reads) in real time which is useful in resolving sequences of complex elements of genomes, such as containing many long repetitive sequences; ii) sequencing de novo (sequencing of DNA with no previously known sequence); iii) and sequencing of full transcripts of mRNA⁴⁷. The most commonly used long-read platforms are manufactured by Pacific Biosciences⁴⁸. In 2014 an innovative approach to single-molecule real time sequencing was developed - **nanopore sequencer**, the MinION from Oxford Nanopore Technologies⁴⁹. In Nanopore technology, DNA passes through a protein pore causing shifts in voltage through the pore, which are characteristic to different sequences of DNA⁵⁰. MinION possess quite unique feature as a sequencer, its small size, comparable to that of a smartphone and therefore portability, as well as exceptionally low price of the instrument (around 1000\$)⁵¹. These features open possibilities of using DNA and RNA sequencing outside conventional laboratories, for example for samples that cannot be transported⁵². Some challenges in nanopore technology, however, remain, such as high error rate and need for equipment used for preparation of DNA libraries⁵³. Other companies also have been developing small size sequencers, or so called DNA sequencing sensors, for example Genapsys (see also Table 5, label: precommercial)⁵⁴. Small size of these devices, low cost and short time of sequencing (when comparing to standard sequencing technologies, see table 6 for comparison) open possibilities of new applications of sequencing⁵⁵, which we describe in the next section (Section 3.2.2). Other manufacturers have been working on

⁴⁵ Levy and Myers, “Advancements in Next-Generation Sequencing”.

⁴⁶ Heather and Chain, “The Sequence of Sequencers: The History of Sequencing DNA”.

⁴⁷ Goodwin, McPherson, and McCombie, “Coming of Age: Ten Years of next-Generation Sequencing Technologies”.

⁴⁸ Ibid.

⁴⁹ Ibid.

⁵⁰ Ibid.

⁵¹ Levy and Myers, “Advancements in Next-Generation Sequencing”.

⁵² Nanopore, environmental research, <https://nanoporetech.com/applications/environmental-research>

⁵³ Goodwin, McPherson, and McCombie, “Coming of Age: Ten Years of next-Generation Sequencing Technologies”.

⁵⁴ Erlich, “A Vision for Ubiquitous Sequencing”.

⁵⁵ Ibid.

new technologies such as microdroplet sequencing⁵⁶, and quantum sequencing⁵⁷, which may improve parameters of sequencing and open new possibilities of application.

In addition, simplified methods of DNA library preparation may be developed enabling one-step in situ library preparation for example microfluidic technique in which library preparation takes place within droplets⁵⁸. Bioinformatic analysis may also be advanced, for example, by usage of *“online bioinformatics pipelines that will align sequence reads as the flow of bases continues to arrive from the basecaller and make on-the-fly decisions before the full data are analyzed, such as pathogen detection from sufficient evidence”*⁵⁹. Such approaches would facilitate further portability and ease of use of sequencing.

Besides read-length, different approaches to sequencing influence also other capabilities and parameters and strengths and weaknesses of sequencing machines, such as throughput (amount of DNA that can be sequenced in a single run), runtime, cost, and error rate⁶⁰.

The data obtained in sequencing needs to be processed using bioinformatic analysis, which usually has an aim to reveal differences between sequenced DNA and a reference genome. These differences may be associated with particular clinical manifestations.

Manufacturer	Amplification	Detection	Chemistry	URL
Commercial				
Illumina	Clonal	Optical	Sequencing by synthesis	http://www.illumina.com
Oxford Nanopore	single molecule	Nanopore	Nanopore	http://www.nanoporetech.com
Pacific Biosciences	single molecule	Optical	Sequencing by synthesis	http://www.pacb.com
Thermo Fisher Ion Torrent	Clonal	Solid state (Change in pH)	Sequencing by synthesis	http://www.thermofisher.com/us/en/home/brands/ion-torrent.html
QIAGEN (GeneReader)	Clonal	Optical	Sequencing by synthesis	http://www.qiagen.com
Precommercial				
Quantum Biosystems	Single molecule	Nanogate	Nanogate	http://www.quantumbiosystems.com
Base4 Single	Single molecule	Optical	Pyrophosphorolysis	http://base4.co.uk

⁵⁶ <http://www.base4.co.uk/microdroplet-sequencing/>, “Microdroplet”.

⁵⁷ Quantum Sequencing, <http://www.quantumbiosystems.com/feature/tech.html?lang=en>.

⁵⁸ Erlich, “A Vision for Ubiquitous Sequencing”.

⁵⁹ Ibid.

⁶⁰ Goodwin, McPherson, and McCombie, “Coming of Age: Ten Years of next-Generation Sequencing Technologies”.

Manufacturer	Amplification	Detection	Chemistry	URL
GenapSys (GENIUS)	Clonal	Solid state	Sequencing by synthesis	http://www.genapsys.com
Roche Genia	Single molecule	Solid state	Nanopore	http://geniachip.com
Postcommercial				
Roche 454 (GS FLX)	Clonal	Optical	Sequencing by synthesis	http://www.454.com
Helicos BioSciences (Heliscope)	Single Molecule	Optical	Sequencing by synthesis	http://www.thermofisher.com/us/en/home/brands/applied-biosystems.html
Dover (Polonator)	Clonal	Optical	Sequencing by ligation	Not available
ThermoFisher Applied Biosystems (SOLiD)	Clonal	Optical	Sequencing by ligation	Not available
Complete Genomics	Clonal	Optical	Sequencing by ligation	http://www.completegenomics.com

Table 5: Summary of next-generation sequencing manufacturers. Precommercial indicates that a NGS platform has been announced but is not yet in sale. Post-commercial means that a platform is not in sale any longer. Adapted from the Table 1 in Shawn E. Levy and Richard M. Myers, ‘Advancements in Next-Generation Sequencing’, Annual Review of Genomics and Human Genetics, 17/1 (2016), 95–115, under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>).

Feature	Sequencing platform	Sequencing sensor
Operation	Static	mobile
I/O	Fancy touch screens	API (application programming interface)
Cost of sequencer	Less important	Important
Cost per bp	Important	Less important
Capacity	Important	Less important
Speed	Less important	Important
Main application	Finding genetic variants	Quantifying DNA molecules
Made for	Human	Machines

Table 6: Sequencing platforms vs. sequencing sensors. Adapted from Table 1 in Yaniv E., ‘A Vision for Ubiquitous Sequencing’, Genome Research, 25/10 (2015), 1411–16 under a Creative Commons License (Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International), as described at <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/>.

Herein we described the basis of the most common approaches of sequencing technologies. Importantly, there are many modifications of these approaches and techniques employing high

throughput technologies in various ways, for different scientific research (for example, single-cell sequencing and RNA sequencing) and clinical purposes (such as for diagnostics in adults or children or for non-invasive prenatal testing, preimplantation genetic diagnosis). These applications are briefly described in the following section.

3.1.2 Applications of high throughput sequencing technologies

NGS is currently used in clinical, research, direct-to-consumer and forensic contexts; use of NGS in all these areas is explored in this subsection. Importantly, in all these contexts NGS can be used with different scope, that is various length of genome areas may be sequenced. Consequently, various amount of data can be created, from which (depending on the scope of analysis) various types and amount of findings can be retrieved. Three types of approaches in NGS may be distinguished:

- **targeted sequencing:** sequencing of selected genes or fragments of a genome related to a set of disorders, for example, cardiomyopathies, immune deficiencies, neurologic disorders, among others. In clinical setting this kind of sequencing approach is usually firstly performed in the context of inherited disorders. When targeted sequencing is not sufficiently informative, approaches listed below are used⁶¹.
- **whole exome sequencing:** involves the sequencing of DNA that codes for proteins. This includes 1-2% of all the DNA in human organisms, and contains around 85% of known disease-causing variants⁶².
- **whole genome sequencing:** obtaining sequence of nearly all DNA of a given organism. In the clinical context, usually trio testing (testing a child and both parents) is performed (also in case of whole exome sequencing) to facilitate analysis and interpretation of the sequence⁶³. Whole genome sequencing has some advantages over whole exome sequencing, such as overall higher ability to detect more variants⁶⁴.

Both in the case of whole genome and exome sequencing a large amount of data is generated. This data can be analysed for a number of purposes, e.g. for carrier screening, predisposition to diseases, to facilitate a diagnosis, to obtain insights into ancestry. Consequently, a wide range of results can be obtained in a single test. However, in a clinical setting, currently whole genome and exome sequencing are performed with a focus on diagnosis or guidance for therapy. Meanwhile, in direct-to-consumer context (see below for more details) genomic sequencing is offered for wider range of purposes.

Research

High throughput sequencing technologies have also wide application in the field of human genomics research, in basic research as well as in research aiming at developing **new methods** or **applications of high throughput sequencing**. The latter type of research is performed in great part by companies selling such technologies (for examples please see Section 3.1.1). Some of the research endeavours which aim at development of new clinical applications and approaches are described in the section below “In future” and in Section 3.1.1 describing sequencing technologies including those that are currently being developed. There are also other developments not outlined in the section below; one

⁶¹ Yohe and Thyagarajan, “Review of Clinical Next-Generation Sequencing”.

⁶² Rehm et al., “ACMG Clinical Laboratory Standards for next-Generation Sequencing.”

⁶³ Yohe and Thyagarajan, “Review of Clinical Next-Generation Sequencing”.

⁶⁴ Levy and Myers, “Advancements in Next-Generation Sequencing”.

of which is single-cell sequencing. DNA analysed in NGS sequencing is usually isolated from a number of cells – this guarantees its appropriate quantity for analysis. For some approaches, however, it is useful to analyse DNA from only one cell, for example, to study heterogeneity and development of some tumours⁶⁵. For such purposes, techniques of single-cell sequencing of DNA and RNA are being developed and increasingly used in research, with an eye on translation into the clinic in the future.

As to **basic research**, genomic technologies can be used to explore variation among genomes in given populations, associations between phenotype and genotype, study function of genes and regulatory elements in genome, and explore interactions between genome and environment⁶⁶. Currently a number of human genomics research projects engaging large cohorts is performed (or have been announced to be launched), for example:

- 100 000 Genome Project in the UK⁶⁷
- “All of Us” in the USA aiming to gather clinical, lifestyle and genomic data from 1 million participants⁶⁸
- A project of a pharmaceutical company Astra Zeneca aiming to collect genome sequences from 2 million people⁶⁹
- A project run by the National Health and Medicine Big Data Nanjing Center in China aiming to sequence 1 million people⁷⁰
- The H3Africa project that extends genomics methods to a wide range of diseases and conditions on the African continent (www.h3africa.org).

Importantly, some of such projects are at the intersection of research and clinical care. An example is the return of results relevant to clinical care of research participants in the UK 100 000 Genomes Project.

Data (and information, both genomic and clinical) gathered in such projects is stored in large databases (genetic databanks) and is often made available for further research. Databases can be available as open-access, that is for anyone, or the access can be limited to certain authorised persons. Genomic databases can be used in clinical practice to facilitate diagnosis. Furthermore, such databanks can be a valuable source of data for researchers. Some genomic consumer companies also collect and store genomic data, for example 23andMe⁷¹. Usually such data are de-identified, that is personal identifying information is removed. Nevertheless, some researchers have indicated the possibilities of relinking personal information to genomic data in certain circumstances⁷². Because of the value of this data for research, some companies charge for providing access to their collections⁷³.

⁶⁵ Navin, “The First Five Years of Single-Cell Cancer Genomics and beyond”.

⁶⁶ Genetics Home Reference, <https://ghr.nlm.nih.gov/primer/genomicresearch/nextsteps>

⁶⁷ 100 000 Genome Project, <https://www.genomicsengland.co.uk/the-100000-genomes-project/>

⁶⁸ NIH Preps National Launch of “All of Us” Precision Medicine Biobank
<https://healthitanalytics.com/news/nih-preps-national-launch-of-all-of-us-precision-medicine-biobank>

⁶⁹ Why big pharma wants to collect 2 million genomes?, <https://www.nature.com/news/why-big-pharma-wants-to-collect-2-million-genomes-1.20697>

⁷⁰ Chinese province sequencing 1 million residents genomes, <https://futurism.com/chinese-province-sequencing-1-million-residents-genomes/>

⁷¹ Sharon, “The Googlization of Health Research: From Disruptive Innovation to Disruptive Ethics”.

⁷² Gymrek et al., “Identifying Personal Genomes by Surname Inference.”

⁷³ Sharon, “The Googlization of Health Research: From Disruptive Innovation to Disruptive Ethics”.

Meanwhile, platforms emerged which offer compensation to individuals if they will share their genomic data for research purposes⁷⁴. Genetic databases may also be created for forensic purposes.

Clinical applications

Currently, NGS in clinical setting is used, among others, for **diagnosis** of a range of diseases, usually those that are idiosyncratic and/or intractable and difficult to associate with any one group of genes or molecules (see Table 7 for the different aims of genetic testing, and in theory, where NGS could also be used, but where it is not necessarily used at the moment). Examples of conditions for which NGS is used in testing include, among others, cardiovascular diseases, hearing loss, neurological diseases. Furthermore, NGS is used for tumour profiling to guide the treatment. Such application can be labelled as pharmacogenomic testing, which aims to predict drug effect on an individual patient⁷⁵ (please see Figure 2 for explanation of pharmacogenomics). Genomic results may also indicate **predisposition** for diseases (for example for breast cancer; usage of NGS in such context may enable preventive measures).

Furthermore, suggestions of using NGS for **newborn screening** have been faced with mixed reactions by different stakeholders; nonetheless pilot projects using NGS in the context of newborn screening programmes were introduced⁷⁶ in the USA to gather more evidence about possible impact of such an application of NGS. Newborn screening programmes aim “*at the early identification in asymptomatic newborns of conditions for which early and timely interventions can lead to the elimination or reduction of associated mortality, morbidity and disabilities*”⁷⁷. Currently, biochemical testing is routinely used in newborn screening, whilst relatively small number of babies undergo genetic testing⁷⁸.

Carrier testing and screening aims to determine if a person carries a gene variant, which may cause a disease in their offspring if the same gene variants is present in the second parent. Some populations have relatively high carrier rates of certain disease (for example Ashkenazi Jewish descents), thus carrier screening is quite common among them⁷⁹. Recently, carrier screening has been also becoming more popular in the USA among the general population⁸⁰.

NGS can also be used to study human genome at early stages of development of a human organism. **Non-invasive prenatal testing (NIPT)** is a technique allowing for analysis of foetal DNA in a maternal blood sample. Unlike other invasive prenatal genetic testing techniques (involving amniocentesis, chorion villus sampling), NIPT does not pose a risk of miscarriage. NIPT is based on analysis of cell free foetal DNA present in the mother’s blood, using NGS technology to compare quantity of, for example chromosome 21, to a reference sample⁸¹. Currently, NIPT, which was introduced to clinical practice in 2011⁸², is increasingly used as a prenatal assay to detect chromosomal aneuploidies, such

⁷⁴ Roberts, Pereira, and McGuire, “Should You Profit from Your Genome ?”

⁷⁵ Rehm, “Evolving Health Care through Personal Genomics”.

⁷⁶ Howard et al., “Whole-Genome Sequencing in Newborn Screening? A Statement on the Continued Importance of Targeted Approaches in Newborn Screening Programmes.”

⁷⁷ Ibid.

⁷⁸ Ibid.

⁷⁹ Rehm, “Evolving Health Care through Personal Genomics”.

⁸⁰ Ibid.

⁸¹ Demkow and Ploski, *Clinical Applications for Next-Generation Sequencing*.

⁸² Allyse et al., “Non-Invasive Prenatal Testing : A Review of International Implementation and Challenges”.

as trisomy 21, trisomy 18, which cause Down syndrome and Edwards syndrome, respectively⁸³. In the countries where prenatal screening programmes are offered, traditionally other genomic or molecular biology technologies have been used to obtain final diagnosis of foetuses having increased risk of a genetic disease. These are chromosomal microarrays and karyotyping performed on a sample obtained by invasive methods (amniocentesis, chorion villus sampling)⁸⁴. Currently, in some countries (the Netherlands, Canada (Ontario)) NIPT has been available as aneuploidy screening test to “high-risk” pregnant women within a public healthcare system⁸⁵. Meanwhile, a number of commercial companies have been offering NIPT, often advertising directly to pregnant women⁸⁶ (as opposite to advertisements targeted to clinicians, see the paragraph on direct-to-consumer genetic testing for more details).

Test type	Purpose description	Current example(s)
Diagnostic testing	To precisely identify a disease and assist in clinical decision-making	Creatine kinase (CK) level testing for Duchenne muscular dystrophy
Predictive testing	To predict the likelihood of developing a disease	<i>HTT</i> gene test for Huntington disease; <i>BRCA</i> gene testing for breast cancer
Carrier testing	To understand the likelihood of passing a genetic disease to a child	<i>CFTR</i> gene testing for cystic fibrosis
Prenatal testing	To identify disease in a fetus	Expanded alpha-fetoprotein (AFP) for risk of neural tube defects, such as spina bifida and Down syndrome
Newborn screening	To determine if a newborn has a disease known to cause problems in health and development	All states must screen for at least 21 disorders by law, and some states test for 30 or more. Metabolic (e.g. classic galactosemia (GALT)), endocrine (e.g. congenital hypothyroidism) and other disorders tested
Pharmacogenomics (PGx) testing	To determine the optimal drug therapy and dose given a person’s metabolic response	The vitamin K epoxide reductase complex subunit 1 (<i>VKORC1</i>) test for likely response to the anticoagulant warfarin. <i>TPMT</i> gene testing for likely response to thiopurine immunosuppressive therapies
Research testing	To contribute to our understanding of	Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) to determine the association of a variant with a

⁸³ Martin et al., “Introduction of Non-Invasive Prenatal Testing as a First-Tier Aneuploidy Screening Test: A Survey among Dutch Midwives about Their Role as Counsellors”.

⁸⁴ Dondorp et al., “Non-Invasive Prenatal Testing for Aneuploidy and beyond : Challenges of Responsible Innovation in Prenatal Screening This Paper Has Been Amended since Online Publication and a Corrigendum Also Appears in This Issue”.

⁸⁵ Vanstone et al., “Women’s Experiences of Publicly Funded Non-Invasive Prenatal Testing in Ontario, Canada: Considerations for Health Technology Policy-Making”; Martin et al., “Introduction of Non-Invasive Prenatal Testing as a First-Tier Aneuploidy Screening Test: A Survey among Dutch Midwives about Their Role as Counsellors”.

⁸⁶ Skirton et al., “Non-Invasive Prenatal Testing for Aneuploidy: A Systematic Review of Internet Advertising to Potential Users by Commercial Companies and Private Health Providers”.

Test type	Purpose description	Current example(s)
	underlying cause of disease	trait

Table 7: Summary of genetic testing. Published in Susan K. Delaney and others, ‘Toward Clinical Genomics in Everyday Medicine: Perspectives and Recommendations’, Expert Review of Molecular Diagnostics, 16/5 (2016), 521–32 licensed Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/>).

Figure 2: Possible results and applications of pharmacogenomic testing. Genomics Education Programme: <https://www.flickr.com/photos/genomicseducation/30312599582/in/photostream/> Shared under Attribution 2.0 Generic (CC BY 2.0) Creative Commons License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/2.0/>).

In the future, NGS is likely to be further integrated into the clinic and used more routinely for some of the aims mentioned above or used for new applications. Some research results indicate possibility of using NGS for preimplantation genetic diagnosis and screening (PGD/S). PGD is an approach allowing for the evaluation of the genetic make-up of embryos on the basis of which they can be selected for implantation to uterus. PGD is used in the context of *in vitro* fertilisation, for example, to increase rate of pregnancies, by eliminating embryos with genetic abnormalities⁸⁷. Currently, most commonly microarray technology is used in PGD⁸⁸. Usage of NGS for PGD has been studied⁸⁹.

DNA sequencing sensors (such as Minilon and Genapsys, see table 6 and previous section) due to their small size, low cost, and short time needed to obtain a sequence may open possibility of new clinical application of sequencing - monitoring/**detecting changes in cell free DNA and RNA in patients in real time**. Cell free DNA and RNA may be used as biomarkers of heart attack, sepsis and brain trauma, and drug overdose⁹⁰. As prognosed by Yaniv Erlich, *“Real-time bedside sequencing at relatively short intervals can serve as the basis for a universal apparatus to capture these biomarkers, adding a new layer of information to patient status”*. Furthermore, DNA sequencing sensors could facilitate diagnosis and surveillance of spreading of infectious diseases (combining data from other sensors), in various environments such as household, hospitals, hotels⁹¹. The author suggests that the sensors may be used for creation of “DNA-aware home appliances”, which would be installed, for example, in toilets to monitor water for presence of pathogens, and microbiomes of persons providing information on the functioning of gastrointestinal system. Another potential application of DNA sensors is analysis of food ingredients/content (including presence of microbes). Additionally, recently MinION sequencing and subsequent analysis of the sequences (“MinION sketching”) was showed to be *“a rapid, inexpensive, and portable strategy to robustly re-identify human DNA”*, which could be used, for example for cell line and tissue authentication/identification in clinical, research and forensic settings⁹². This could help avoid mix-ups of samples and eliminate usage of contaminated cell-lines in research⁹³.

Consumer genomics

Importantly, the health-related applications of NGS testing outlined above are, to a great extent, offered also by companies which sell and/or advertise testing directly to consumers. Some such tests can be purchased directly by a consumer, others have to be ordered with an involvement of a physician. The direct-to-consumer genetic testing (DTC GT) market has been vividly expanding in recent years, not only with respect to the number of companies, but also the range of products on offer (for example tests for newborns, prenatal testing) and approaches employed (e.g. whole exome

⁸⁷ Kurahashi et al., “Preimplantation Genetic Diagnosis/screening by Comprehensive Molecular Testing”.

⁸⁸ Fiorentino et al., “Application of next-Generation Sequencing Technology for Comprehensive Aneuploidy Screening of Blastocysts in Clinical Preimplantation Genetic Screening Cycles”.

⁸⁹ Treff et al., “Evaluation of Targeted next-Generation Sequencing – Based Preimplantation Genetic Diagnosis of Monogenic Disease”.

⁹⁰ Erlich, “A Vision for Ubiquitous Sequencing”.

⁹¹ Ibid.

⁹² Zaaijer et al., “Rapid Re-Identification of Human Samples Using Portable DNA Sequencing”.

⁹³ Ibid.

and genome sequencing)⁹⁴. The market of direct-to-consumer genetic testing is predicted to continue to grow in the coming years⁹⁵. Remarkably, recently Ramji Srinivasan, co-founder and chief executive of a consumer genomics company Counsyl has expressed bold plans for the firm: “*making expanded carrier screening as routine as taking folic acid, non-invasive prenatal screening as routine as an ultrasound, and hereditary cancer screening as well-known as a pap smear.*”⁹⁶

Importantly, DTC GT companies offer testing not only for health-related purposes. There is a range of offers aimed to inform consumers on choices related to diet, sport predispositions, ancestry, or even partner choices⁹⁷. Of concern is that some of such offers are not supported by scientific research.

Forensic and security applications

Genetics is also used in the context of forensics. The currently most commonly used approach in forensic genetic analysis involves analysis of short tandem repeats (STRs), DNA sequences which include a variable number of short (2–6 bp) and repeated sequence motifs, such as (GATA)_n. STR loci are amplified using polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and detected in capillary electrophoresis. The variability (polymorphism) of STR lengths in the human population allows one to distinguish DNA samples from different persons, and when comparing with DNA from databases, identification of a person. STR analysis is also used to determine kinship (including paternity)⁹⁸.

Next generation sequencing enables new approaches in forensic DNA analysis by making them potentially more cost-effective. Predictive phenotyping based on DNA sequence analysis may provide insights into externally visible characteristics, such as eye and hair colour, as well as biogeographical ancestry. Biographical ancestry analysis indicates ancestral origin, which can be useful in populations which are heterogenous regarding this feature. These approaches could also facilitate study and identification of decomposed human remains⁹⁹. Predictive phenotyping has already been used in a small number of criminal investigations¹⁰⁰. Development of DNA sequencing sensors (see previous section) may in the future further facilitate criminal investigations by enabling fast analysis of DNA samples at crime scenes. While highly contentious, Erlich suggests that DNA sensors may also be used for security control purposes, for example at airports¹⁰¹.

⁹⁴ Niemiec, Kalokairinou, and Howard, “Current Ethical and Legal Issues in Health-Related Direct-to-Consumer Genetic Testing”.

⁹⁵ Hayden, “The Rise, Fall and Rise Again of 23andMe”.

⁹⁶ Counsyl, <https://blog.counsyl.com/2017/11/06/counsyl-celebrates-10-year-anniversary-with-new-financing-and-new-board-member/>

⁹⁷ Branca, “Reproducing with DNA”; Kalokairinou, Howard, and Borry, “Direct-to-Consumer Genetic Testing”.

⁹⁸ Kayser and de Knijff, “Improving Human Forensics through Advances in Genetics, Genomics and Molecular Biology”.

⁹⁹ Scudder et al., “Massively Parallel Sequencing and the Emergence of Forensic Genomics: Defining the Policy and Legal Issues for Law Enforcement”.

¹⁰⁰ Ibid.

¹⁰¹ Erlich, “A Vision for Ubiquitous Sequencing”.

3.2 Technologies modifying genome

3.2.1 Description of technologies

The first approaches to alter DNA sequences appeared in the early 1970s, allowing scientists to modify DNA in bacteria. In the next decades, various genome engineering approaches have been introduced. Importantly, in the last few years new innovative technology was developed - a new tool for **site-specific gene editing**, known as **CRISPR-Cas9** (Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats Cas-associated nuclease 9)¹⁰². In this subsection of section 3, we will focus on this novel genomic approach and its applications, however, gene editing tools are not the only means of introducing changes to the human genome. Table 8 lists other molecular biology approaches currently used (either in clinic and/or in research) to introduce changes in human genomes.

Technique	Current applications in Humans (unless specified)
Gene editing or Genome editing	Germline: research Somatic: research and clinical trials
“Traditional” gene therapy	Germline: - Somatic: research and clinic
Mitochondrial replacement/Nuclear transfer	Germline: research and clinic Somatic: not applicable
Somatic Nuclear transfer	Only in non-human animals, and other organisms

Table 8: List of techniques used to modify human genome.

In initial attempts to modify or interact with the human genome (as opposed to “just¹⁰³ studying” it in the context of subsection 3.1: reading its sequence or alluding to its structure) viral vectors have been used to deliver extraneous DNA to cells. Such DNA would be inserted into the genome of target cells and replace or disrupt a malfunctioning gene, with the ultimate aim of having a therapeutic effect. Currently, many such **gene therapies** are being tested in clinical trials¹⁰⁴, while a few are already available in the market as drugs¹⁰⁵. New gene editing tools, mentioned above and described in more detail below, also may be used for gene therapies, offering advantages over the conventional gene therapy approaches, such as possibility of introducing targeted and precise changes¹⁰⁶.

Nuclear transfer techniques are other approaches allowing for introduction of changes to human genome. They allow for what is called **“mitochondrial replacement”** in which the nucleus is transferred from one embryo (or oocyte before fertilization) with mutated DNA in its mitochondria to an embryo (or oocyte before fertilization) with healthy DNA in the mitochondria. This process is conducted in the context of IVF and requires additional third-party embryos or oocytes with “healthy” mitochondria. Mitochondrial replacement aims at preventing passing maternal

¹⁰² Doudna and Charpentier, “The New Frontier of Genome Engineering with CRISPR-Cas9”.

¹⁰³ With all due respect to Franklin, Watson and Crick and other scientists who « just » studied the (human) genome, the recent advances in technologies to modify the genome so efficiently do extend the limits of what can be done in a spectacular fashion.

¹⁰⁴ Wirth, Parker, and Ylä-Herttuala, “History of Gene Therapy”.

¹⁰⁵ Senior, “After Glybera’s Withdrawal, What’s next for Gene Therapy?”

¹⁰⁶ Maeder and Gersbach, “Genome-Editing Technologies for Gene and Cell Therapy”.

mitochondrial diseases on offspring. The procedure has already been conducted in the clinical setting, despite the concerns related to technical problems raised by this technique¹⁰⁷. Moreover, recently, the U.K. Human Fertilisation and Embryology Authority (HFEA) approved a clinical trial in which mitochondrial replacement will be used in context of IVF with aims to establish a pregnancy¹⁰⁸. Of note, the usage of mitochondrial replacement in clinics constitutes the first case of germline modification conducted in a clinical setting. Nonetheless, mitochondrial replacement is a different type of germline modification than site specific changes which may be introduced by gene editing, as described in the remainder of this section 3.2.1

An approach of nuclear transfer may be used yet for another purpose (however different in some aspects from the one described above) – to obtain an embryo/organism with genome (almost) identical to the original one, in other words to clone an organism. Such technique, **somatic cell nuclear transfer**, involves a transfer of the nucleus from an adult cell (for example a skin cell) to an oocyte in which the nucleus was removed. If successful, this technique produces a clone carrying identical nuclear DNA of the original adult organism, which was achieved in a number of mammalian species¹⁰⁹. Importantly, in the beginning of 2018 another animal, a macaque monkey was successfully cloned, a species more similar to human organisms than other previously cloned animals and in which somatic cell nuclear transfer was more difficult to conduct¹¹⁰. As to cloning humans, although a few groups of scientists claimed in the past of achieving this, these reports ultimately were shown to be unsubstantiated¹¹¹. To date there is no solid evidence of successful cloning of a human¹¹², and no openly known attempts by “serious”/recognised scientists to do so. Nevertheless, this ethically contentious topic has been subject of debates regarding legitimacy of its use, which may now be reignited as a consequence of the above-mentioned progress in cloning primates¹¹³.

Importantly, a few types of human cloning can be distinguished, based on its purpose:

- therapeutic cloning: created embryo would be used to obtain totipotent embryonic stem cells, which are immunologically compatible with the original organism and can serve it for therapeutic purposes¹¹⁴ but without the aim to let the embryo develop into a foetus.
- reproductive cloning: aiming at creating a human person being a clone of another one, obtained embryo would be implanted into uterus to establish pregnancy
- research cloning: cloned embryos would be created solely for research purposes, for example to obtain insights into embryo development or into properties of derived embryonic stem cells.

Undoubtedly, applications of all the techniques outlined above introduce profound social, legal and ethical implications, which are important to consider and address. However, in the remainder of this report we will focus on gene editing, given the time constraints and the fact that the other approaches are not specific to genomics per se, but rather to cellular and molecular biology. Of note,

¹⁰⁷ Connor, “When Replacement Becomes Reversion”.

¹⁰⁸ U.K. Human Fertilisation and Embryology Authority (HFEA), <https://www.hfea.gov.uk/about-us/news-and-press-releases/2017-news-and-press-releases/hfea-statement-on-mitochondrial-donation/>

¹⁰⁹ Liu et al., “Cloning of Macaque Monkeys by Somatic Cell Nuclear Transfer”.

¹¹⁰ Ibid.

¹¹¹ Cloning Fact Sheet, <https://www.genome.gov/25020028/cloning-fact-sheet/#al-8>

¹¹² Ibid.

¹¹³ Chadwick, “Reproductive Cloning”.

¹¹⁴ Rhind et al., “Human Cloning: Can It Be Made Safe?”

some, if not many of socio-ethical issues/impacts of gene editing overlap with other technologies, such as problems related to instrumentalization of embryos and legitimacy of introducing heritable changes to the human genome, which are discussed in Section 4.

Gene editing technologies

The CRISPR-Cas 9 system was discovered to be an adaptive immune system response in bacteria¹¹⁵. It consists of guide RNA, which allows identification of a DNA sequence and Cas9 enzyme, which subsequently cuts the identified sequence (for details see Figure 3). In 2013 the first experiments were conducted showing that CRISPR-Cas9 can be engineered to target and modify a chosen gene sequence¹¹⁶. The ways of delivering CRISPR-Cas9 to various types of cells, including human cells were developed, for example using viral transduction, cell microinjections or electrophoresis^{117,118} (Figures 3 and 4).

Current Opinion in Virology

¹¹⁵ Doudna and Charpentier, “The New Frontier of Genome Engineering with CRISPR-Cas9”.

¹¹⁶ Ibid.

¹¹⁷ Gulei and Berindan-Neagoe, “CRISPR/Cas9: A Potential Life-Saving Tool. What’s Next?”

¹¹⁸ Van Erp et al., “The History and Market Impact of CRISPR RNA-Guided Nucleases”.

Figure 3: Methods of delivery of Cas9 system and dsDNA break repair processes. This figure was published under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>) in Paul B.G. Van Erp and others, 'The History and Market Impact of CRISPR RNA-Guided Nucleases', Current Opinion in Virology, 12 (2015), 85–90.

Single guide RNA (sgRNA) contains a sequence homologous to target DNA in cells, which enables localization and delivery of Cas9 protein to the target DNA sequence. Nuclear localization signal (NLS, a sequence of amino acids) is added to Cas9 protein to target it to nucleus in eukaryotic cells, which unlike bacteria store most of DNA in the nucleus. Protospacer adjacent motif (PAM) is a DNA sequence following the targeted DNA sequence; PAM is identified by Cas9 protein. Cas9 cleaves DNA causing double strand DNA break, which is subsequently repaired by cell's endogenous non-homologous end joining (NHEJ) or homology directed repair (HDR). In the process of NHEJ (which is preferentially used by cells) additional nucleotides are inserted (so called indels) or deleted causing genes knock-outs (that is disruption of gene function). NHEJ, therefore, is not useful for gene correction applications of gene editing. If a sequence homologous to the one cleaved by Cas9 is present in cells, HDR will take place resulting in insertion of a sequence present in the homologous DNA sequence which is used as a template in the repair process. Therefore, in application of Cas9 to correct a given DNA sequence, an exogenous DNA is delivered to cells, which is then used as a template in HDR process¹¹⁹. However, as shown in the study of Ma et al.¹²⁰, in heterozygous zygotes a wild type copy of gene can be used as a template to correct its mutant copy in HDR process¹²¹.

¹¹⁹ Ma et al., "Correction of a Pathogenic Gene Mutation in Human Embryos."; Van Erp et al., "The History and Market Impact of CRISPR RNA-Guided Nucleases".

¹²⁰ Ma et al., "Correction of a Pathogenic Gene Mutation in Human Embryos."

¹²¹ In fact, in Ma et al. (2017) study, the wild type template/the maternal template seemed to have been almost the sole sequence used, which differs from results obtained in cultured cells. The reason and mechanism for this remain unknown.

Figure 4: Various methods of delivering CRISPR/Cas9 system to cells and strategies of curing diseases using CRISPR/Cas9. The figure was published in: Morgan L Maeder and Charles A Gersbach, ‘Genome-Editing Technologies for Gene and Cell Therapy’, *YMTHE*, 24/3 (2016), 430–46 under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Before the introduction of CRISPR-Cas9 other gene editing tools, such as zinc finger nucleases (ZFNs) and Transcription Activator-Like effector nucleases (TALENs) were used in research for well over a decade¹²². CRISPR-Cas9, however, has allowed for much faster and easier design of the system to target a specific sequence, than it used to be with ZFN and TALEN enzymes¹²³. Furthermore, increased efficiency, specificity, and lower price are features which distinguish CRISPR-Cas9 from the other tools. Therefore, although these earlier approaches were proven useful, CRISPR-Cas9 has brought a revolution in the field of genome engineering. Yet, some challenges in applying of CRISPR-Cas9 still need to be overcome. These include, overcoming off-target effects, efficacy and reliability, improving delivery to chosen tissues, and enhancing function.

3.2.2 Applications of gene editing technologies

Basic research

Currently gene editing is used in basic research in the context of human genomics both on human somatic cells and human germline cells/embryos (in countries where this is allowed).

Germline gene editing

Basic research on human embryos has aims, among others to provide insights into embryo development, which may be relevant in the future to understand infertility, and to improve the practice of *in vitro* fertilization, for example to increase the success rates of conceiving. Furthermore, these kinds of studies may provide information about safety and efficiency of gene editing, which may be proven useful in future similar experiments as well as for potential endeavours of applying gene editing in clinical settings (should this be deemed allowable by law and ethical standards). Embryos (and embryonic stem cells) may also be engineered with gene editing to study diseases and subsequently drugs and treatments¹²⁴. This involves producing loss-of-function mutants, which have disrupted function of given genes. While not performed in human cells, germline gene editing is used to develop model organisms (e.g. drosophila, mice, rabbits) of human diseases which help scientists further understand the mechanisms of the disease and can eventually help in some way to manage (cure, treat, prevent) the disease in humans.

Somatic gene editing (on human cell lines)

Somatic gene editing in basic research on human cell lines is used among others, to study cancer development. For example, CRISPR-Cas9 system is used to introduce chromosomal translocations similar to these appearing in cancers (e.g. lung cancer, myeloid myeloma). Furthermore, CRISPR-Cas9 may be applied for studies of gene functions, by introducing loss-of-function changes in genes, which can be used for example to detect genes necessary for viability of cells in cancer. Usage of CRISPR-

¹²² Benjamin et al., “Therapeutic Genome Editing : Prospects and Challenges”.

¹²³ Van Erp et al., “The History and Market Impact of CRISPR RNA-Guided Nucleases”.

¹²⁴ Wert et al., “Responsible Innovation in Human Germline Gene Editing . Background Document to the Recommendations of ESHG and ESHRE”.

Cas9 to disrupt function of given genes is employed also for screening for phenotypes and drug targets. Finally, CRISPR/Cas9 may be used to correct faulty genes causing inherited diseases (e.g. cystic fibrosis)¹²⁵ in human cell lines.

In this report, when referring to such uses of gene editing in a research setting, however with an eye on clinical applications we will be using the term “pre-clinical research” as opposed to basic research which does not necessarily open a path to potential clinical applications. Indeed, the term pre-clinical research is not consistently used in the academic literature and seems to be primarily used by industry, where the entire aim is to eventually have their research be translated into clinical use. While it was difficult to find any definitive mapping of pre-clinical versus basic research and pre-clinical versus clinical-research, we have proactively decided to group “pre-clinical” with clinical given the large ramifications of confusing the term with “basic” research. For example, one of our concerns is that when policy documents are drafted, decisions could be made to agree to the use of gene editing in basic and pre-clinical research with an understanding that pre-clinical does not necessarily imply clinical research thereafter. However, given the confusion of the terms pre-clinical and clinical research, and the fact that the former appears to be used in a context where there is an *a priori* expectation to eventually arrive to the clinical research stage, we want to avoid that recommendations originally labelled under “basic” research be transferred without serious reflection to the context of clinical research.

Pre-clinical research, clinical research and potential clinical applications

Currently, research on gene editing aiming in developing clinical applications focuses mainly on somatic gene editing for monogenic (caused by a mutation in a single gene) life-threatening diseases. Below, we present overview of applications of gene editing in somatic and germline human cells. Gene editing may be used to cure genetic diseases either by disrupting function of a gene which codes for a protein which causes a disease so that this protein is not produced any more (for example, in hemoglobinopathies) or by correcting “faulty” DNA sequence by inserting correct sequence (e.g. cystic fibrosis)¹²⁶.

Somatic gene editing

A number of diseases are being currently studied both in preclinical studies and clinical trials; details are outlined in Tables 9 and 10. Some of the approaches studied, for example, with potential to be used in patients with HIV, have already proved safe enough¹²⁷. Yet others are still in their initial phases. Some of the companies which have commercial interest in CRISPR-Cas9 technology are listed in Table 11.

Target	Strategy
Viral infections	
HIV	Inactivating HIV receptors (CCR5, CXCR4)
	Knocking out essential host factors (LEDGF/p75)
	Excising viral genomes

¹²⁵ Doudna and Charpentier, “The New Frontier of Genome Engineering with CRISPR-Cas9”.

¹²⁶ Maeder and Gersbach, “Genome-Editing Technologies for Gene and Cell Therapy”.

¹²⁷ Tebas et al., “Gene Editing of CCR5 in Autologous CD4 T Cells of Persons Infected with HIV”.

Target	Strategy
	Targeted integration of antiviral factors
Hepatitis B virus	Inhibiting viral replication
Herpes simplex virus	Inhibiting viral replication
Human papilloma virus	Inactivating essential viral genes
T-cell immunotherapy	Knocking out endogenous T-cell receptors
	Knocking out self antigens
	Knocking out glucocorticoid receptor
	Knocking out checkpoint inhibitors
Hematologic disorders	
X-SCID	Gene correction in T cells and CD34+ HSCs
ADA-SCID	Gene modification in cell lines
RS-SCID	Gene correction in patient iPSCs
Sickle cell disease and β-thalassemia	Correction of β -globin mutations in iPSCs
	Correction of β -globin mutations in CD34+ HSCs
	Inactivation of the enhancer of BCL11A
Liver-targeted gene editing	
Hemophilia	Targeted cDNA addition to endogenous gene
Enzyme replacement	Targeted gene addition to albumin locus for hemophilia and lysosomal storage disorders
Tyrosinemia type I	Gene correction in mouse liver
PCSK9	Gene disruption in mouse liver to lower cholesterol
α-1-antitrypsin deficiency	Gene correction in human iPSCs and differentiation into liver cells
Neuromuscular disorders	
Duchenne muscular dystrophy	Ex vivo targeted insertion of missing exons
	Ex vivo targeted insertion of a therapeutic minigene
	Ex vivo frameshift correction by NHEJ
	Ex vivo reading frame restoration by exon deletion
	In vivo reading frame restoration by exon deletion
Skin disorders	
Epidermolysis bullosa	Gene correction in fibroblasts and iPSCs
Ocular disorders	
Leber's Congenital Amaurosis type 10	Deletion of an aberrant splice site
Respiratory disorders	
Cystic fibrosis	Gene correction in stem cells
	Gene correction in mouse lung epithelium
Antimicrobials	
Bacterial infection	Reduction of bacteria in infection models
	Removal of bacteria using type I CRISPR systems

Table 9. Representative preclinical studies of gene editing for gene and cell therapy. Adapted from Morgan L Maeder and Charles A Gersbach, 'Genome-Editing Technologies for Gene and Cell Therapy', YMTHE, 24/3 (2016), 430–46 under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Identifier	Phase	Title	Status as of October 2015
NCT00842634	Phase 1	Autologous T Cells Genetically Modified at the CCR5 Gene by Zinc Finger Nucleases SB-728 for HIV	Completed
NCT01044654	Phase 1	Phase 1 Dose Escalation Study of Autologous T Cells Genetically Modified at the CCR5 Gene by Zinc Finger Nucleases in HIV-Infected Patients	Completed
NCT01082926	Phase 1	Phase I Study of Cellular Immunotherapy for Recurrent/Refractory Malignant Glioma Using Intratumoral Infusions of GRm13Z40-2, An Allogeneic CD8+ Cytolytic T Cell Line Genetically Modified to Express the IL 13-Zetakine and HyTK and to be Resistant to Glucocorticoids, in Combination With Interleukin-2	Completed
NCT01252641	Phase 1/2	Study of Autologous T Cells Genetically Modified at the CCR5 Gene by Zinc Finger Nucleases in HIV- Infected Subjects	Completed
NCT02225665	Phase 1/2	Repeat Doses of SB-728mR-T After Cyclophosphamide Conditioning in HIV-Infected Subjects on HAART	Active
NCT01543152	Phase 1/2	Dose Escalation Study of Cyclophosphamide in HIV-Infected Subjects on HAART Receiving SB-728-T	Recruiting
NCT02500849	Phase 1	Safety Study of Zinc Finger Nuclease CCR5-modified Hematopoietic Stem/Progenitor Cells in HIV-1 Infected Patients	Recruiting

Table 10: Representative ongoing and completed gene-editing clinical trials. This table was published in: Morgan L Maeder and Charles A Gersbach, 'Genome-Editing Technologies for Gene and Cell Therapy', *YMTHE*, 24/3 (2016), 430–46 under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Industry sector	Product/application	Company	Intellectual property
Medical	Pharmaceuticals	Novartis	Caribou License
	<i>In vitro</i> applications only	Cellectis	Boston Children's Hosp., Institut Pasteur License
	Target validation	AstraZeneca	Open Innovation Model
	Therapeutics	Crispr Therapeutics	PCT/US2013/032589
	Monogenic diseases	Sangamo	PCT/US2013/032381; PCT/US2013/039979; PCT/US2013/028348
	Therapeutics	Biosciences	Caribou License
	Therapeutics	Intellia Editas	Broad, Duke, MGH Licenses
Laboratory	Research tools	System Biosciences	US 14/216 655
	Expression systems	Sigma-Aldrich	PCT/US2013/073307
	Research tools	GE Healthcare	Broad License
	Animal models	Sage	Caribou, Broad License

Industry sector	Product/application	Company	Intellectual property
	Research tools	ThermoFisher	Collectis Sublicense
	Animal models	Taconic	Broad License
Sublicensing	Ag, Industrial, Bio	Caribou	PCT/US2013/053287

Table 11: Industry interests in Cas9-based technologies, adapted from Table 1 published in under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>) in Paul B.G. Van Erp and others, ‘The History and Market Impact of CRISPR RNA-Guided Nucleases’, *Current Opinion in Virology*, 12 (2015), 85–90.

Germline gene editing

Some authors suggest that the use of CRISPR-Cas9 or other similarly effective gene editing tools, (if refined and proved safe enough) may have a potential for **eliminating genetic causes of monogenic inherited diseases** at the early stage of development of a human organism, that is in fertilized oocyte (zygote) and embryo, or even before fertilization, that is in germline cells. Importantly, these approaches would have to be conducted in the context of *in vitro* fertilization.

In April 2015, a study of a research group led by Junjiu Huang was published reporting first successful use of CRISPR-Cas9 gene editing in (non-viable) human embryos¹²⁸. The researchers aimed to modify β -globin gene (which if mutated causes β -thalassemia) in zygotes (one-cell embryos) discarded in the clinic. Although CRISPR-Cas9 system cleaved β -globin gene in zygotes, the efficiency of repair process, which would replace the gene with its ‘correct’, non-mutated version was low. Furthermore, the scientists reported off-target events, that is modifications of other non-target sites of the genome and mosaicism, that is occurrence of cells with different genotypes (e.g. where a given gene is modified in some cells, but not in all of them) in one embryo. A year after the study of Liang et al. was published, another CRISPR-Cas9 experiment on non-viable embryos was described. This time, scientists introduced an allele of a gene which is associated with a resistance or slower progression of HIV infections¹²⁹. Kang et al. also reported technical problems such as mosaicism of embryos¹³⁰.

Importantly, in 2017, other studies involving CRISPR-Cas9 were published involving **viable** embryos (created for the purposes of the research or being surplus embryos obtained in IVF). A study of Chinese scientists described correction of two point mutations related to a common enzyme deficiency (which causes, for example anaemia) and β -thalassemia¹³¹. In August 2017 another article appeared, which described correction of a mutation that causes hypertrophic cardiomyopathy in heterozygous preimplantation viable embryos (which had been created for the sole purpose of this research project)¹³². Ma et al. (2017) suggested also a method of delivery of CRISPR-Cas9 system (injecting CRISPR-Cas9 to oocyte together with sperm), which reduces mosaicism in embryos. Yet, complete elimination of mosaicism was not achieved in that study. Mosaicism in clinical context would render verification of gene editing results in embryos problematic. In addition, the exact effect

¹²⁸ Liang et al., “CRISPR/Cas9-Mediated Gene Editing in Human Trippronuclear Zygotes”.

¹²⁹ Kang et al., “Introducing Precise Genetic Modifications into Human 3PN Embryos by CRISPR / Cas-Mediated Genome Editing”.

¹³⁰ Ibid.

¹³¹ Tang et al., “CRISPR/Cas9-Mediated Gene Editing in Human Zygotes Using Cas9 Protein”.

¹³² Ma et al., “Correction of a Pathogenic Gene Mutation in Human Embryos.”

of mosaicism on phenotype of an organism is not known, therefore, mosaicism remains an obstacle which would preclude possible clinical application of the method¹³³.

Currently, if prospective parent(s) carry a mutation which causes a disease in their progeny, in order to avoid having offspring affected by that disease (and have genetically related offspring), they may opt for *in vitro* fertilization (IVF) procedure and preimplantation genetic diagnosis (PGD). PGD may identify embryos which do not carry specific disease-causing mutation. These embryos would then be transferred to the uterus; embryos identified as carrying given mutation would be discarded or potentially used in research if parents agree. CRISPR-Cas9 in this context could be applied in embryos carrying disease-causing mutations and consequently increase the number of “healthy” embryos which would be transferred to uterus, which might potentially increase pregnancy rates¹³⁴.

In some very rare cases, IVF and PGD may not be helpful in achieving the goal of genetically-related offspring not affected by diseases inherited from their parents. Such situations are where both parents are homozygous (have two copies of a “faulty” gene) for a recessive disorder or when one parent is homozygous for a dominant disorder, which results in all their embryos/children carrying disease-causing configuration of genes. For parents in this situation who wish to halt the transmission of the pathogenic variant to their offspring, they may consider using donated gametes from a third party for in-vitro fertilization, adopting a child or not having children. In such a situation CRISPR-Cas9, by modifying ‘faulty’ genes in the embryos, might introduce the potential of eradicating the disease while allowing a couple to have genetically related progeny. Notably, application of gene editing to homozygous zygotes might pose challenges; gene editing of two copies of a given gene (that is, in homozygous embryos) was not yet shown in preclinical research. Specifically, the challenges are related to the repair process which would introduce the correct copy of gene - securing efficient homology-direct repair process necessary for correction of mutant genes would be problematic in homozygous embryos¹³⁵ (see figure 3 for description of homology-direct repair process).

In the situations described above, CRISPR-Cas9 also has the potential to be used on germ cells from which eggs and sperm are derived, instead of on embryos¹³⁶. The corrected gametes would then be used in the context of artificial reproductive technologies. This approach, however, raises technical challenges and has not been yet tested in human cells¹³⁷.

Furthermore, some predict that CRISPR-Cas9 could be applied in human induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) (derived for example from skin cells), from which, after correcting a faulty gene, by gene editing, gametes would be derived¹³⁸. The “corrected” gametes would be then used in the context of artificial reproductive technologies to create an embryo and establish pregnancy. Creation of gametes from stem cells was described in mice, but has not been shown in humans¹³⁹, therefore the possibility described above currently remains theoretical.

¹³⁴ Ma et al., “Correction of a Pathogenic Gene Mutation in Human Embryos.”

¹³⁵ Sherkow, “The CRISPR Patent Landscape: Past, Present, and Future”.

¹³⁶ Vassena et al., “Genome Engineering through CRISPR/Cas9 Technology in the Human Germline and Pluripotent Stem Cells”.

¹³⁷ Ibid.

¹³⁸ Ibid.

¹³⁹ Ibid.

Do-it-yourself (DIY) gene editing

Interestingly, now gene editing may be available not only to researchers, but to anyone who can afford purchasing a kit advertised online. These gene editing kits are designed to be used in bacteria and yeasts and are unproven for uses in humans. Despite this, in October 2017, a biohacker Josiah Zayner, CEO of a company selling such kits injected himself with, as he described “DNA that contains the Cas9 protein and a guide RNA (gRNA) targeted to the exon 1 of the Myostatin gene”, produced by his laboratory¹⁴⁰. Zayner alleges that this complex would target and disrupt the function of myostatin gene, which would result in increased muscle growth¹⁴¹. Self-experiments using gene-editing kits sold by the company of Zayner (for yeast and bacteria modifications) are not able to introduce changes to individuals’ genome, as this would require more sophisticated methods of delivery¹⁴². However, experts warn that such self-experimentation poses risks of an adverse immune reaction to the injected DNA. The U.S. Food and Drug Administration also warned consumers:

“Consumers are cautioned to make sure that any gene therapy they are considering has either been approved by FDA or is being studied under appropriate regulatory oversight.”¹⁴³

CRISPR/Cas9 gene editing, due to the ease with which it can be used, introduces possibility of expansion of DIY gene therapy uses. Cases of administering unproved gene therapies, however, appeared before CRISPR/Cas9 was developed. In 2015, a CEO of a US company BioViva developing gene therapies, received two therapies under development aiming to increase muscle mass and extend telomere caps which would slow aging¹⁴⁴. Also in that case, important questions about scientific validity and safety were raised and such applications remain highly speculative.

Please consult section 4 of this report to access additional information on the social and economic impacts of (potential) modifications of the human genome.

¹⁴⁰ The first attempt at human CRISPR gene editing, <http://www.ifyoudontknownowaknow.com/2017/10/the-first-human-to-attempt-crispr-gene.html>; Biohackers disregard FDA warning on DIY gene therapy, <https://www.technologyreview.com/s/609568/biohackers-disregard-fda-warning-on-diy-gene-therapy/>.

¹⁴¹ The first attempt at human CRISPR gene editing, <http://www.ifyoudontknownowaknow.com/2017/10/the-first-human-to-attempt-crispr-gene.html>

¹⁴² Biohackers disregard FDA warning on DIY gene therapy, <https://www.technologyreview.com/s/609568/biohackers-disregard-fda-warning-on-diy-gene-therapy/>

¹⁴³ Information about self administration of gene therapy, <https://www.fda.gov/BiologicsBloodVaccines/CellularGeneTherapyProducts/ucm586343.htm>.

¹⁴⁴ Dance, “Better Beings?”

Section 4. Survey of social and economic impacts of technologies used in Human Genomics

4.1 Introduction

In order to more fully grasp the consequences of technologies used in Human Genomics, as well as consider how concrete impacts may help us address a (more) complete list of ethical issues, we looked to the social and economic impacts of genomic technologies. Formal socio-economic impact evaluations are usually conducted for a specific technology applied for a specific purpose (e.g. using next generation sequencing for the identification of specific pathogenic variants for the diagnosis of cystic fibrosis), on a specific population (e.g. in a specific country, e.g. the Netherlands, or in a specific sub-population, the Québec founder population from the Saguenay- Lac-St-jean region) and for a given period of time (e.g. 2016-2021) (for an example, please see Castonguay et al. 2012)¹⁴⁵. Given the following limiting factors, it was impossible to perform such a formal socio-economic impact assessment (SEIA): the limited time of the SIENNA project as a whole, and consequently the limited time possible to allocate for this task; the large scope of genomics requested to be addressed, including a large number of genomic technologies, and the possible applications of these; as well as the lack of access to specific data (for example, about a health-care system costs of implementation of a given genomic technology). Indeed, one could extrapolate this problem to being a particular problem for the SEIA of emerging technologies, which by the very fact that they are emerging and not entrenched in use, would mean that there are no, or very little, concrete numbers on which to base a formal SEIA. Therefore, herein we present a more *general* survey of current and expected social and economic impacts of human genomic technologies based on the review of available academic literature, publicly accessible information from grey literature, and our own expertise in both the science of genomics, as well as the ethics of genomics. In the following sections we first present the discussion of social and economic impacts for sequencing technologies followed by a discussion on genome editing technologies.

4.2 Methods

Our first approach to provide a comprehensive account of the socio-economic impacts resulting from the diffusion of high throughput technologies of genome sequencing was to collect reviews of the literature (i.e. to conduct an umbrella review) through online databases such as PUBMED, the social science research network (SSRN), ScienceDirect and web tools (Google Scholar). Search terms used include:

- Social / next generation sequencing* / review
- Social / whole genome sequencing* / review
- Social/genomics/review
- Ethic / next generation sequencing* / review
- Ethic / whole genome sequencing* / review

¹⁴⁵ Castonguay, Marcellis-Warin, Mishagina, "Evaluating the Potential Socio-Economic Impact of Personalized Medicine"

- Ethic/genomics/review
- Economic / next generation sequencing* / review
- Economic / whole genome sequencing* / review
- Cost / next generation sequencing* / review
- Cost / whole genome sequencing* / review

* for the section on the modification of the genome, the middle term was replaced by terms like genome modification, gene modification, genome editing, gene editing,

For the review of literature for the social and economic impacts of technologies used to study the “genome”, this search did not provide results regarding general usage of genome sequencing technologies but the reviews collected addressed social, ethical and economic issues specific to the use of these technologies¹⁴⁶. The second step of our search was then setting-specific (for ELSI of techs used to study the genome). Based on the setting mentioned in the resources (e.g. clinic, research lab, public health programme) reviews collected and our expertise of the key discussions and key authors in each field, we then chose to focus on a less comprehensive and more strategic approach to the search. In this way, we could highlight specific social and economic impacts of the diffusion of high throughput genome sequencing and gene editing technologies that were not arising through the initial search strategy. We searched for academic studies but also industry, policy and media reports that addressed the social and economic dimensions of genome sequencing in research, in the clinic, in public health and in forensics.

Since the diffusion of high throughput technologies has already started in each of these settings, we also looked for sociological and anthropological literature that described some of the social trends we had previously identified as accompanying this diffusion:

- Medicalization: a process by which some non-medical aspects of human life come to be considered as medical problems¹⁴⁷;
- Geneticization¹⁴⁸: ‘an on-going process by which differences between individuals are reduced to their DNA codes, with most disorders, behaviours and physiological variations defined, at least in part, as genetic in origin’¹⁴⁹;
- New eugenics (neo-eugenics, consumer eugenics, liberal eugenics, and libertarian eugenics): an ideology which advocates the use of reproductive technologies where the choice of “enhancing”¹⁵⁰ human characteristics is left to the individual preferences of parents acting as consumers, rather than the public health policies of the state¹⁵¹.

For the review of the literature for the social and economic impacts related to technologies to modify the genome, we started with a corpus of literature already gathered by one of the authors (HCH) for

¹⁴⁶ Colleen and Cho, “Ethical, Legal, Social and Policy Implications of Behavioral Genetics”; Williams and Wienroth, “Social and Ethical Aspects of Forensic Genetics: A Critical Review”.

¹⁴⁷ Moynihan, Doust, and Henry, “Preventing Overdiagnosis: How to Stop Harming the Healthy”.

¹⁴⁸ Lippman, “Prenatal Genetic Testing and Screening: Constructing Needs and Reinforcing Inequities”; Lippman, “The Genetic Construction of Prenatal Testing”; Lippman, “Led (Astray) by Genetic Maps: The Cartography of the Human Genome and Health Care”; Arribas-Ayllon, “After Geneticization”.

¹⁴⁹ Lippman, “Prenatal Genetic Testing and Screening: Constructing Needs and Reinforcing Inequities”.

¹⁵⁰ The use of the word enhancement in this definition does not necessarily follow the description advocated in the SIENNA Deliverable WP3.1.

¹⁵¹ Duster, *Backdoor to Eugenics*.

an article that reviewed the ELSI of gene editing in Humans (Howard et al. 2017) and then branched out from that by using the references found in these articles.

This review of the literature allows us to report on contemporary discussions about the socio-economic impacts of genomic science and technology in support of research, clinics, public health and forensics. Although not mutually exclusive, these debates emphasize different features of genome sequencing technologies, and their location within wider social structures.

4.3 Technologies to explore the genome —high-throughput DNA sequencing technologies

4.3.1 Introduction

DNA sequencing is not new. It was first described in 1977 by Maxim and Gilbert¹⁵² and Sanger et al¹⁵³. Subsequent decades of improvements to the Sanger method have increased sequencing efficiency and accuracy. At each step, more sophisticated DNA sequencing technologies (i.e. sequencers, programs, and bioinformatics) have provided more automation and higher throughput¹⁵⁴. Because of the rapid evolution in this field, and the replacement of older approaches with newer ones, we will not address present and future socio-economic impact of high throughput technologies of genome sequencing at the early stage of technological research & development but rather at the later stage of technological use and **diffusion**.

Diffusion is an extremely critical process for the practical use of innovation. It can be defined as the process by which *“an innovation is communicated through certain channels over time among the members of a social system”* and by which alteration occurs in the structure and function of a social system as a ‘kind of social change’¹⁵⁵. We use this framework to address **the social and economic impacts of the diffusion of high throughput technologies of genome sequencing in research, in the clinic, in public health and in forensics**. As a result of this diffusion, there are indeed not only technical but also cultural and organizational changes¹⁵⁶ that are now occurring (– or are expected to occur) which will result in socio-economic consequences in each of these contexts.

Due to the large scope of human genomics (which was the scope we were tasked to address) it is impossible for us, in this report, to also address the social and economic impacts of genomics used in agriculture, in farm-animals and in insects and microorganisms. While we recognize that these contexts have direct and important impacts on human lives, addressing them herein would easily triple if not quadruple the size of this work and the time needed to properly address these areas. We, however, strongly urge for study of these areas and for the results to be discussed within the wider context of human and planetary health and sustainability.

¹⁵² Maxim and Gilbert, “A New Method for Sequencing DNA.”

¹⁵³ Sanger, Nicklen, and Coulson, “DNA Sequencing with Chain-Terminating Inhibitors”.

¹⁵⁴ García-Sancho, *A New Insight into Sanger’s Development of Sequencing: From Proteins to DNA, 1943-1977*.

¹⁵⁵ Rogers, *Diffusion of Innovation (5th Ed.)*.

¹⁵⁶ Pacey, *The Culture of Technology*.

4.3.2 Economic impact of the diffusion of high throughput sequencing technologies

Sanger sequencing (first generation sequencing), is considered the standard of sequencing methodologies. It has a very high degree of specificity, but also a low level of throughput which makes the process of sequencing expensive and time consuming. This is why developers have sought out novel methods for genetic sequencing that would allow for increases in throughput and potential cost reduction¹⁵⁷. The first breakthrough towards second-generation sequencing, also called next generation sequencing (NGS), was published in 2005. Since then, NGS approaches (which allow entire exomes and genomes to be sequenced) have been used in research settings and are increasingly becoming standard practice in clinical settings.

The markets of genome sequencing technologies

The NGS market, including but not limited to whole genome sequencing (WGS), was valued at €4.6Bn globally in 2015 and is expected to reach €20Bn by 2020¹⁵⁸. Many private companies, such as Illumina, Roche, Life Technologies and Pacific Biosciences, have invested a lot for the diffusion of sequencers.

Besides the industrial markets working on the technology development and sequencing services, some companies are trying to capitalize on the wealth of data. The most well-known may be 23andme (<https://www.23andme.com/en-int/>), a personal genomics company whose stated goal is to help people access and understand their genome. The product to be purchased is an at-home genetic test kit directly marketed directly to consumers, accompanied with a service in the form of an online interface through which users can view and interpret their results. In addition to the fee-for-service model, the power of the 23andMe business model comes from the value of their database, which includes the aggregated data of over 2million customers¹⁵⁹. These data provide an important resource for research at different levels and can potentially be accessed by public or private entities which are willing to pay.

There is also a market of data storage specifically developed for genomic data¹⁶⁰. Amazon (https://aws.amazon.com/health/genomics/?nc1=h_ls) and Google (<https://cloud.google.com/genomics/?hl=fr>) for instance offer to keep a copy of any genome for €24 (\$25) a year, which translates to roughly €0.02/GB per month, since a file is commonly between 100 and 400GB.

The declining cost of genome sequencing

The move from Sanger sequencing to next-generation sequencing technologies has lowered the cost of sequencing. The cost of sequencing a whole genome was estimated to be around US\$10 million in 2007 (NHGRI 2016); this fell to below \$1,500 in 2015 and should fall under \$1,000 (NHGRI 2016) in the near future¹⁶¹. This cost is considered an “affordable” in many high-income countries. Once affordable, according to the health care standards typical in such countries, genome sequencing

¹⁵⁷ Metzker, “Emerging Technologies in DNA Sequencing”; Jarvie, “Next Generation Sequencing Technologies”; Margulies et al., “Genome Sequencing in Microfabricated High-Density Picolitre Reactors”.

¹⁵⁸ Timmerman, “DNA Sequencing Market Will Exceed \$20 Billion, Says Illumina CEO Jay Flatley”.

¹⁵⁹ Steinberg, Horwitz, and Zohar, “Building a Business Model in Digital Medicine”.

¹⁶⁰ Regalado, “Google Wants to Store Your Genome: For \$25 a Year, Google Will Keep a Copy of Any Genome in the Cloud”.

¹⁶¹ Church, “The Race for the \$1000 Genome”.

could be used routinely in health care or even in public-health programs (e.g. on a population-wide basis) for medical and other purposes¹⁶².

However, most cost estimates within the literature (including those produced by the NHGRI for whole-genome sequencing) tend to focus on the cost of resources used to run platforms but do not capture the large costs of the downstream analysis and interpretation of data that make genomic testing meaningful and useful in clinics.

“The cost of a complete sequencing service includes DNA preparation and is dependent on the number of samples required; sequencing coverage and depth; the number of reads; the platform used; general laboratory costs, such as overheads and skill mix (for example, salary costs for the relevant grade of molecular scientist or bioinformatician); resources needed for data analysis and interpretation; and the capacity to deliver a sufficient number of tests.”¹⁶³

Genome-sequencing practices should thus be considered as encased within broader infrastructure. In the clinic, the cost of genome sequencing should span four components: (1) the technology; (2) the diagnostic component; (3) the model of service delivery to provide the diagnostic test and (4), if appropriate, subsequent treatment options¹⁶⁴.

Challenges in the evaluation of genome sequencing cost-effectiveness

There are three overall processes that have been developed in NGS: whole genome sequencing (WGS), whole exome sequencing (WES) and targeted gene sequencing (TGS). WGS denotes the sequencing of the entire genome while WES and TGS are more focused on specific parts of the genome. WES focuses on only the protein coding regions of the genome. TGS is the most focused and examines specific genes or regions of interest (specified a-priori by the laboratory) making it of key interest to clinical investigations. The costs associated with any one of these approaches (WGS, WES, TGS) vary greatly depending on the methodology used, the gene or genes being investigated, and the laboratory that is conducting the analysis¹⁶⁵. It is also very difficult to determine cost effectiveness of NGS due to the multifaceted nature of the interpretation of results, which requires experts from various different backgrounds such as molecular, clinical and genetic counseling¹⁶⁶.

Studies aiming to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of genomic technologies generally conclude that there is a lack of economic investigations published to date¹⁶⁷. To give an idea of the scarcity of these evaluations, the few attempts to appreciate the cost-effectiveness of genomic technologies can be compared with the related field of precision medicine, where 45 systematic reviews of economic evaluations of precision medicine have been published to date, while there were no published economic evaluations of new sequencing technologies until recently¹⁶⁸. This is a result of the

¹⁶² Robertson, “The \$1000 Genome: Ethical and Legal Issues in Whole Genome Sequencing of Individuals”.

¹⁶³ Payne et al., “Cost-Effectiveness Analyses of Genetic and Genomic Diagnostic Tests”.

¹⁶⁴ Ibid.

¹⁶⁵ Wright et al., *Next Steps in the Sequence. The Implications of Whole Genome Sequencing for Health in the UK*.

¹⁶⁶ Frank et al., “Genome Sequencing: A Systematic Review of Health Economic Evidence”.

¹⁶⁷ Ibid.

¹⁶⁸ Payne et al., “Cost-Effectiveness Analyses of Genetic and Genomic Diagnostic Tests”.

complexity of analyzing the costs associated with all processes subsequent to the sequencing run itself¹⁶⁹.

The budget impact of genomic tests in the clinic

The budget impact of introducing genomic tests into a health-care system – which involves knowing the health-care resources required to implement testing and then potentially changing management or treatment – is harder to quantify than the cost of performing sequencing. To date no accurate published figures exist for the total budget impact of introducing genetic or genomic tests into practice¹⁷⁰. Some specific budget impacts have however been calculated within specific conditions. In the UK, the budget impact of introducing whole-exome sequencing to the diagnostic pathway for patients with a high probability of having a rare inherited disease and who attend special genetic services, was estimated to increase pathway cost of £939 per patient (or a 52.5% increase) compared with the usual testing strategy¹⁷¹. Evaluating the cost-effectiveness of a specific genomic technology involves a medical evaluation as to the suitability of the technology for diagnostic purposes (that is, its capacity to provide an actionable test result) and an organizational examination that allows the service delivery to be offered to the relevant patient population.

But defining the relevant population can be problematic for genomic tests. For example, when considering the added value of whole-genome sequencing, the relevant patient population may extend beyond the index patient first tested and include family members (sometimes referred to as spillover effects). Including spillover effects into the calculation introduces another problem that compounds how to conceptually define a lifetime: it is indeed no longer obvious if the valuation of a clinical pathway spans the lifetime of one patient or if it spans generations¹⁷².

Evolution of job markets in relation with the diffusion of genome sequencing

In clinical laboratories, the diffusion of genome sequencing may favor a transition from a model where cytogeneticists and clinical biochemical geneticists are primarily required to a model where clinical molecular geneticists and biostatisticians will be more needed. This transition may operate differently according the settings, but considering the healthcare budget constraints, chances are that the latter may be replaced by the former and will not provide a net increase in jobs.

With the increase in use of genomics in medicine, some stakeholders have suggested that the profession of genetic counselors will play increasingly important role¹⁷³. Others have reflected how competences of genetic counsellors have to be developed to allow appropriate practice of genetic counselling in the context of the offer of genomic technologies¹⁷⁴. Of course, this will depend greatly on how the education and profession of genetic counseling is established, considered and/or accepted within medicine in any one country or region¹⁷⁵. Genetic counselors are professionals who

¹⁶⁹ Ibid.

¹⁷⁰ Ibid.

¹⁷¹ Sagoo et al., “The Budget Impact and Cost-Effectiveness of Introducing Whole-Exome Sequencing-Based Virtual Gene Panel Tests into Routine Clinical Genetics”.

¹⁷² Payne et al., “Cost-Effectiveness Analyses of Genetic and Genomic Diagnostic Tests”.

¹⁷³ Well, “Genetic Counselling in the Era of Genomic Medicine”.

¹⁷⁴ Swanson, Ramos, and Snyder, “Next Generation Sequencing Is the Impetus for the Next Generation of Laboratory-Based Genetic Counselors.”

¹⁷⁵ Pestoff, Ingvaldstad, and Skirton, “Genetic Counsellors in Sweden: Their Role and Added Value in the Clinical Setting”.

have specialized education in genetics and counseling to “to help people understand and adapt to the medical and psycho-social consequences of either having, being at-risk from or passing on a genetic condition”¹⁷⁶. They work with geneticists but also with obstetricians, oncologists and other doctors (for example in cardiovascular and neurology departments). In some countries, like the UK, there is a formal training programme and genetic counselors play an established and recognized role in the genetics clinic. Meanwhile, in other countries, like Sweden, the education of genetic counseling is less formalized and the exact place in the clinical offer of genetic testing is not as established or clear¹⁷⁷.

Lastly, while mostly speculative, some have questioned whether the genetic clinic itself would be transformed completely by the mainstreaming of genomics in medicine. It has been suggested that instead of having specialists in all or “general” genetics in one delineated or dedicated clinical group, other specialists like cardiologists and oncologists would become specialized in cardiogeneticists and oncogeneticists respectively. While this model may apply for more common complex disorders like cardio- or onco-disorders, it is important to remember that the more “general” genetics clinic will likely still be needed for rare monogenetic syndromes which by virtue of their complex phenotypes will not easily fit into one medical specialty (not to mention the new, ultra-rare or familial syndromes that spring up, especially in parts of the world where consanguineous marriages remain the norm.

The complexity of pharmacogenomics development

Economic considerations are at the ground of pharmacogenomic developments: not only is it supposed to increase drug efficiency and to minimize side effects but, doing so, substantial savings should be realized by eliminating costs associated with failed treatment¹⁷⁸. There are however extensive discussions among economists, both on the pharmaceutical industrial side to inform investment decisions and on the payer side (government, industry and society), to make coverage decisions, so as to evaluate if upfront testing costs will be offset by avoided nonresponse costs¹⁷⁹.

Firstly, evaluating the economic impact of genetic or genomic testing on healthcare delivery and cost is always a challenge¹⁸⁰, so this obviously remains an issue when considering the cost of pharmacogenomics¹⁸¹. Second, the industrial model of development of pharmacogenomics is challenging existing models of drug development and clinical practice. Some aspects of the pharmacogenomic enterprise may indeed not be feasible to implement under current business frameworks, and others represent threats to existing organizations¹⁸² or to reconsider intellectual property landscape¹⁸³. There are however reasons to believe that there could be clear benefits in investing in pharmacogenomics when considering the big picture of drug development from innovation to market delivery:

¹⁷⁶ Middleton et al., “Direct-to-Consumer Genetic Testing: Where and How Does Genetic Counseling Fit?”

¹⁷⁷ Pestoff, Ingvaldstad, and Skirton, “Genetic Counsellors in Sweden: Their Role and Added Value in the Clinical Setting”.

¹⁷⁸ Stallings et al., “A Framework to Evaluate the Economic Impact of Pharmacogenomics”.

¹⁷⁹ Deverka, Vernon, and McLeod, “Economic Opportunities and Challenges for Pharmacogenomics”.

¹⁸⁰ Payne et al., “Cost-Effectiveness Analyses of Genetic and Genomic Diagnostic Tests”.

¹⁸¹ Phillips et al., “Genetic Testing and Pharmacogenomics: Issues for Determining the Impact to Healthcare Delivery and Costs”.

¹⁸² Ginsburg et al., “Implications of Pharmacogenomics for Drug Development and Clinical Practice”.

¹⁸³ Kirk et al., “Implications of Pharmacogenomics for Drug Development”.

“The sales may decrease because the drug is not used for non-responders, however, the number of subjects necessary for a clinical trial can be reduced, study period can be shortened and the drug can be marketed earlier. Furthermore, adverse events (AE) and adverse drug reactions (ADR) during the clinical trial and post-marketing phase can be markedly reduced. This represents a great benefit for the patients, pharmaceutical companies and the society as a whole.”¹⁸⁴

The main issue today (and in the near future) is to provide robust clinical evidence of the benefits of pharmacogenomics tests¹⁸⁵. More research is also needed to assess patient preferences and willingness to pay for genomic technologies; how providers can assess and use genomic technologies; and how the industry, insurers, and government can best balance the relevant costs and benefits¹⁸⁶. As pharmacogenomics involves a population to be stratified by response to a drug, there are also several issues to be discussed in terms of solidarity so as to ensure that its development would not affect our understanding of the importance of universal health care¹⁸⁷.

The question of the cost of pharmacogenomics should also be addressed at a global level, since the genetically diverse African population is for instance likely to benefit from a pharmacogenomics-based healthcare approach. The reduction of drug side effects, and separation of responders and non-responders could lead to optimized drug choices and doses for each patient, with respect to communicable and non-communicable diseases (like HIV, malaria, sickle cell disease and cardiovascular diseases) that are particularly frequent in Sub-Saharan Africa¹⁸⁸.

In its statement about Pharmacogenomics, HUGO thus mentions that solidarity (because of shared vulnerabilities, people have common interests and moral responsibilities to each other) and equity (to reduce health inequalities between different populations, and to work towards equal access to care is an important prerequisite for implementing genomic knowledge for the benefit of society) have to be taken into considered prior concerns when developing pharmacogenomics¹⁸⁹.

4.3.4 Social impact of the diffusion of high throughput sequencing technologies

Investigating the ethical, legal and social dimensions of genomic research has been acknowledged as a substantial and necessary part of the research process since the initial assessment of the plans for the Human Genome Project¹⁹⁰. This work has been given formal recognition in 1990 with the establishment of the Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications (ELSI) Program, as a component of the Project¹⁹¹. From there, the term ELSI has evolved to now label an academic discipline aiming to

¹⁸⁴ Ohashi, Mizushima, and Tanaka, “Economic Advantage of Pharmacogenomics-Clinical Trials with Genetic Information”.

¹⁸⁵ Berm et al., “Economic Evaluations of Pharmacogenetic and Pharmacogenomic Screening Tests: A Systematic Review. Second Update of the Literature”.

¹⁸⁶ Phillips et al., “Genetic Testing and Pharmacogenomics: Issues for Determining the Impact to Healthcare Delivery and Costs”.

¹⁸⁷ Prainsack, “The ‘We’ in the ‘Me’ Solidarity and Health Care in the Era of Personalized Medicine”.

¹⁸⁸ Mpye et al., “Disease Burden and the Role of Pharmacogenomics in African Populations”.

¹⁸⁹ Committee, “HUGO Statement on Pharmacogenomics (PGx): Solidarity, Equity and Governance”.

¹⁹⁰ Committee on Mapping and Sequencing the Human Genome, *Mapping and Sequencing the Human Genome*.

¹⁹¹ McEwen et al., “The Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications Program of the National Human Genome Research Institute: Reflections on an Ongoing Experiment”.

inform the development of a relevant (and responsible) policy framework for the development of genomics and genetics. This abundant ELSI literature has highlighted several aspects of genomics susceptible to causing social issues – sometimes worthy of a formal policy response. Below we address potential social concerns and impacts grouped by area of use of genomics: in research, during transfer to the clinic, in the traditional health care clinic, in commercial direct-to-consumer contexts, in public health, and in forensics. While we have grouped potential social impacts in this way, it is important to note that many of the concerns overlap and are shared by the different contexts of use of genomics.

Social impact of genomic research

Genetic patents

Patents on human gene sequences have been controversial since such patenting ideas emerged¹⁹². Patent litigation has since now mainly focused on gene patents for therapeutic protein (e.g. insulin, growth hormone, and erythropoietin¹⁹³), there is however a larger societal discussion about the possibility that gene patents may prevent certain research endeavors and even obstruct clinical access, thus leading to unjustified deaths¹⁹⁴.

Potential harm for participants

Besides issues on privacy¹⁹⁵, confidentiality¹⁹⁶, and informed consent¹⁹⁷, other ethical issues in genomic research include the possibility to withdraw from research¹⁹⁸, return of research results¹⁹⁹ (including the right not to know) and public data release²⁰⁰.

Genetic discrimination

Reports predicting the emergence of a new “genetic underclass” which would be excluded from many aspects of social life (for example, unable to get life or health insurance, or being discriminated against in getting a job) have emerged in scientific and popular media over the past two decades²⁰¹. Genetic discrimination is thus perceived as a social threat requiring policy responses. In Europe, in the US and in Australia, a plethora of laws, guidelines and policies have been adopted, both at the regional (Council of Europe, European Union) and national level^{202 203}. For example, in the US, the

¹⁹² Eisenberg, “A Technology Policy Perspective on the NIH Gene Patenting Controversy”.

¹⁹³ Cook-Deegan and Heaney, “Patents in Genomics and Human Genetics”.

¹⁹⁴ Crichton, “Patenting Life”.

¹⁹⁵ Lin, Owen, and Altman, “Genomic Research and Human Subject Privacy”.

¹⁹⁶ Lowrance and Collins, “Ethics. Identifiability in Genomic Research.”

¹⁹⁷ Master et al., “Biobanks, Consent and Claims of Consensus”; Gibson and Copenhaver, “Consent and Internet-Enabled Human Genomics”; Ducournau, “The Viewpoint of DNA Donors on the Consent Procedure”.

¹⁹⁸ Karimi-Busheri, *Biobanking in the 21st Century*.

¹⁹⁹ Appelbaum et al., “Models of Consent to Return of Incidental Findings in Genomic Research.”

²⁰⁰ Bull, Roberts, and Parker, “Views of Ethical Best Practices in Sharing Individual-Level Data From Medical and Public Health Research: A Systematic Scoping Review”.

²⁰¹ Lemmens, “Selective Justice, Genetic Discrimination, and Insurance: Should We Single out Genes in Our Laws”; Martin, Greenwood, and Nisker, “Public Perceptions of Ethical Issues Regarding Adult Predictive Genetic Testing”.

²⁰² Joly, Braker, and Le Huynh, “Genetic Discrimination in Private Insurance: Global Perspectives”.

Genetic Information Nondiscrimination Act addresses health insurance and job discrimination ²⁰⁴.

Exacerbate health disparities

Although many researchers and clinicians may “*overstate the potential benefits of genetic research to alleviate and eventually eliminate health disparities*”²⁰⁵, in fact, applications of genomic technologies could exacerbate, rather than ameliorate, health disparities between racial and ethnic groups. This could happen, for example, by focusing research (funds) on biological causes of disease instead of more compelling social and environmental risk factors.

Another concern comes from the fact that allele frequencies in genes associated with various diseases are known to differ by racial and ethnic groups, when the populations enrolled in studies of disease risk often lack diversity on this dimension ²⁰⁶. In these conditions, genomic research may lead to further health disparities.

Social impact of genome sequencing during technology transfer

‘Technology transfer’ may refer to diverse phenomena²⁰⁷. It generally consists in the development of a technology in one setting that is then transferred for use in another setting²⁰⁸. In our context, it consists in all the movements of know-how and technical knowledge that accompany the implementation of high throughput technologies of genome sequencing from research to clinic, ie. from the organizational and institutional setting where these technologies were developed to generate genomic knowledge to another organizational and institutional setting where they will serve clinical applications.

Technology transfer should thus be interpreted in a holistic perspective, which includes both the movement of technology from the site of origin to the site of use and issues concerning the ultimate acceptance and use of the technology by the end user²⁰⁹. Routine clinical use of high throughput technologies, for example, requires technological enhancements (higher accuracy and better ways to select genomic subsets of interest), but also substantial enhancements in laboratory computer infrastructure, data storage, and data transfer capacity; training of clinicians and laboratory personnel to use the sequence data effectively; and appropriate procedures to deal with the incidental discovery of pathogenic mutations and variants of uncertain clinical significance²¹⁰.

In theory, and ideally, the implementation of new genetic tests into the clinic depends on the evaluation by different experts of each specific test’s (including the specification of disease, variant, population and methodology) analytic validity, clinical validity, clinical utility, associated ethical, legal

²⁰³ Otlowski, Taylor, and Bombard, “Genetic Discrimination: International Perspectives”.

²⁰⁴ Feldman, “The Genetic Information Nondiscrimination Act (GINA): Public Policy and Medical Practice in the Age of Personalized Medicine”.

²⁰⁵ Sankar et al., “Genetic Research and Health Disparities”.

²⁰⁶ Bustamante, Burchard, and De la Vega, “Genomics for the World”.

²⁰⁷ Selinger, “Technology Transfer: What Can Philosophers Contribute?”

²⁰⁸ Markert, *Contemporary Technology: Innovations, Issues, and Perspectives*.

²⁰⁹ Johnson, Gatz, and Hicks, “Expanding the Content Base of Technology Education: Technology Transfer as a Topic of Study”.

²¹⁰ Soulier, Julia, and Cambon-Thomsen, “A Review of Ethical Questions Raised by the Transfer into Clinics of Massive Parallel Sequencing Technologies”.

and social implications²¹¹ as well as their cost-effectiveness²¹² – all aspects then being compared with current tests (for the same specifications). In practice, for a number of practical, logistical, and financial reasons, this does not necessarily always happen, even for “simple” single gene tests. For the translation of high throughput sequencing into the clinic, given the fact that the tool itself is not meant to search for a single variant for a specific disease, the underlying assumptions for using evaluations like the ACCE framework are greatly challenged²¹³. Indeed, such evaluations are highly complex, including among others, the evaluation of clinical utility of these new methods²¹⁴ and their associated ELSI²¹⁵. If genome sequencing has the potential to transform the practice of medical genetics and related fields, the vast amount of personal genomic data produced will also increase the responsibility of geneticists to ensure that the information obtained is used in a medically and socially responsible manner.

The social impact of the technological transfer, which is happening currently in many different European and North American countries mostly via pilot projects in the clinic, thus depends on the comprehensive views adopted during the evaluation process. As to the transfer itself, premature translation without the adequate professional support or ELSI policy frameworks, as well as disparities in access should be taken into consideration as with any new health care technologies. These raise social and moral concerns about justice, disparities in access to both testing and intervention, and the differing risks and benefits that may result given different socioeconomic status or racial background.

Social impact of genome sequencing in clinic

Clinical use of genome sequencing provides a way to identify the cause of rare and/or intractable diseases of unknown etiology through the screening of thousands of loci for pathogenic mutations. Clinical sequencing is also used to sequence biological specimens for the genomic signatures of novel infectious agents. It is expected “to improve diagnosis and management of some disorders with a strong heritable component, as well as improve personalized diagnosis and personalized drug therapy and treatment”²¹⁶. In some clinical contexts, high throughput sequencing technologies are replacing array and sanger sequencing technologies thanks to the formers’ dropping cost, increased throughput and automated processes.

Certain features of genome sequencing, which set it apart from more ‘traditional’ clinical genetics, are critical to understand the ELSI:

- Genome sequencing gives rise to significant volumes of information;
- Not all of it is yet understood with respect to interpretation of whether variants are

²¹¹ Sanderson et al., “How Can the Evaluation of Genetic Tests Be Enhanced? Lessons Learned from the ACCE Framework and Evaluating Genetic Tests in the United Kingdom”.

²¹² Payne et al., “Cost-Effectiveness Analyses of Genetic and Genomic Diagnostic Tests”.

²¹³ Howard and Iwarsson, “Mapping Uncertainty in Genomics”.

²¹⁴ Grosse and Khoury, “What Is the Clinical Utility of Genetic Testing?”; McPherson, “Genetic Diagnosis and Testing in Clinical Practice.”; Hastings et al., “The Changing Landscape of Genetic Testing and Its Impact on Clinical and Laboratory Services and Research in Europe.”

²¹⁵ Burke, Pinsky, and Press, “Categorizing Genetic Tests to Identify Their Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications”.

²¹⁶ Howard et al., “Whole-Genome Sequencing in Newborn Screening? A Statement on the Continued Importance of Targeted Approaches in Newborn Screening Programmes.”

- “normal” or pathogenic, hence the meaning or interpretation of sequencing data will almost certainly change with time;
- Genome sequencing will not always lead to certainty (e.g. one clear answer to the molecular diagnosis or cause of a disease), and may introduce new uncertainties.

These critical features create specific issues depending on “how and when” genome sequencing is implemented in the course of clinical care. Genomics for instance challenges presumptions, such as whether the mere possibility of applications of a technology should lead to a wide implementation (technological imperative). This stands in sharp contrast with the vision according to which clinical questions or needs should rather guide the use of new technologies. Yet, when the individual being tested is a fetus or a child, these considerations become even more significant in order to assure responsible use of new technologies.

Genome sequencing in adults

Clinical genetic testing in adults is at present typically done for a relatively small number of patients who, as a result of family history or clinical indications, are considered at risk of carrying genetic variations that are linked to a particular disease or disease predisposition. Compared with present clinical genetic testing, genome sequencing greatly expands the breadth of testing from genes associated with a particular disease to large parts of the genome and, potentially, all the information that the genome contains about diseases or traits. Genomic sequencing is expected to be diffused into current genetic services but also eventually into health care as a whole; in this way, sequencing data or genomic data will be taken into consideration for more common complex diseases (e.g. forms of cancer, diabetes, cardiac diseases).

Clinical genetic testing examines only a few risks (or variants in genes associated with disease), which are specified in advance, but genome sequencing will potentially provide information about countless medical conditions that go beyond the initial question of the clinical consultation. As part of the interpretation of genome sequencing, analysis could show that patients have slightly altered genetic risks for common adult diseases such as cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and various cancers. These disorders have both genetic and environmental components; some might have useful interventions, but others will not. Sequencing might also reveal information about risks for sensitive issues, such as psychiatric disorders²¹⁷ or behavioural traits²¹⁸. Moreover, in view of the predicted frequency of recessive mutations in the population, every patient will learn that he or she is a heterozygous carrier of more than one serious or lethal autosomal recessive disease. This information might affect a patient’s reproductive decisions, and have implications for relatives.

“Since whole genome sequencing analysis is likely to reveal that every patient has an above-average risk for some disorder(s), and for having children with some disease with a genetic component, every patient could face some negative social consequences from these genetic risk factors, whether in insurance, employment, stigma, or otherwise.”²¹⁹

²¹⁷ Smoller et al., “Psychiatric Genetics and the Structure of Psychopathology”.

²¹⁸ Colleen and Cho, “Ethical, Legal, Social and Policy Implications of Behavioral Genetics”.

²¹⁹ Ormond et al., “Challenges in the Clinical Application of Whole-Genome Sequencing”.

This leads to a fascinating discussion in terms of the temporality of the technologies diffusion, because, if in the long run, recognition of the universality of risk might lead to improved social support, here and now, exposed patients might suffer²²⁰.

As for any emergent technology, there are risks for vulnerable populations to be excluded from novel opportunities for care. This is even more the case for patients whose results will need to be reassessed in view of changing information. Genomic results are indeed interpreted in view of present knowledge but considering our evolving understanding of the genome, that knowledge is expected to evolve. Some potential risk-variants will have disappeared and new risk-variants will have been reported. The magnitude of the risks will change as will our knowledge of the interaction of particular genomic risks with other genomic variations and with the environment. The benefits of genome sequencing thus rely on the capacity of the health care system developed to update information already conveyed, which makes it particularly sensitive to disparities in healthcare access.

Furthermore, as was mentioned previously for genomic sequencing in research, genomic sequencing in the clinic will also face similar ELSI challenges, not the least because in this era of big data and biobanking research endeavors seem to be a pre-set part of any clinical offer. Some of these ELSI include: privacy and confidentiality; informed consent for both the clinical and research aspects; return of results, including incidental and secondary findings as well as long term recontact as new knowledge is generated; public data release and commercialization to third parties; communication with family members of results; evolving roles and responsibilities of different health care professionals towards patients, their family and society as genomics enters health care.

Pediatric genome sequencing

Genome sequencing is gradually being implemented in pediatric genetics clinic. It should help obtain a diagnosis for children and families and provide an optimized treatment. Although genome sequencing has the potential to positively impact clinical practice, mitigate the effects of illness and improve quality of life for some children and their families, there are several concerns related to the use of genomic testing for children – especially regarding consent and privacy.

Until recently, the consensus approach to genetic testing and screening in general has reflected cautious limitations on the use of genetic testing on children. In particular, predictive genetic testing was seen as justified only when clear clinical indications called for genetic information; when clear treatment or prevention could start in childhood to help alleviate or treat the condition²²¹. Indeed, the fact that parents would consent for genetic testing on the behalf of their child (who is not able to provide consent, but from whom assent should be obtained) has raised the issue of the child's right not to know (about genetic information). In the research context, which, as mentioned above is increasingly attached to the clinical context, there are proposals to recontact children once they reach the age of majority in order to give them the opportunity to consent for themselves whether or not they want their samples and data to be kept for research²²².

²²⁰ Ibid.

²²¹ Borry et al., "Predictive Genetic Testing in Minors for Adult-Onset Genetic Diseases".

²²² Gurwitz et al., "Children and Population Biobanks"

Of course, all the other ELSI raised previously for adults also apply here, as well as in the contexts below, but one could consider that with each context including (more) vulnerable stages of life, these ELSI are amplified. Please note that the case of genomic sequencing used at the newborn stage is treated below under the “public health” context.

Fetal genome sequencing

The amount of genetic and genomic information obtainable from the human fetus during pregnancy is accelerating at an unprecedented rate. Two trends have dominated recent technological advances in prenatal diagnosis: the exploration of the fetal genome in increasingly high resolution and the development of non-invasive methods of fetal testing using cell-free DNA in maternal plasma²²³. These developments aim towards the facilitation of autonomous reproductive choice²²⁴. In the future, it is thus possible that a pregnant woman will be proposed more or less systematically a first-trimester blood test that will inform her as to “*whether her fetus has a chromosome abnormality and/or dozens of single gene mutations, and/or thousands of polymorphisms*”²²⁵.

The discovery of cell-free fetal DNA in maternal plasma in 1997 stimulated a rapid development of non-invasive prenatal testing²²⁶. With the advent of massively parallel sequencing (MPS), the sensitivity and precision with which one can analyse circulating fetal DNA for non-invasive prenatal testing (NIPT) have been greatly enhanced. However, the current knowledge of the pathogenic implications, if any, of many genomic aberrations remains incomplete. Thus, the premature implementation of NIPT that would cover such aberrations would create difficulties in counseling and might generate unnecessary patient anxiety at a time when they are particularly vulnerable²²⁷. This is especially a concern when certain commercial vendors provide such tests in a direct-to-consumer setting, which might allow patients to gain access to such tests without any or adequate counseling and having clinical professionals to monitor the performance of such tests²²⁸.

Besides, the relative ease of performing NIPT compared with conventional invasive testing has raised the question as to whether the routinization of such developments would encourage more women to undergo prenatal testing for screening purposes than would otherwise be the case. This possibility aligns with a strong sense, coming from the sociological and anthropological literature, that ‘natural’ biological parenthood is coming to be perceived as something that is “*in need of being managed, assisted, monitored*”²²⁹. There is also the concern that NIPT might be used for non-medical indications, e.g. sexing for social reasons²³⁰.

²²³ de Jong, Maya, and van Lith, “Prenatal Screening: Current Practice, New Developments, Ethical Challenges”.

²²⁴ Dondorp et al., “Non-Invasive Prenatal Testing for Aneuploidy and beyond: Challenges of Responsible Innovation in Prenatal Screening”.

²²⁵ Hui and Bianchi, “Recent Advances in the Prenatal Interrogation of the Human Fetal Genome”.

²²⁶ Lo et al., “Maternal Plasma DNA Sequencing Reveals the Genome-Wide Genetic and Mutational Profile of the Fetus”.

²²⁷ McGillivray et al., “Genetic Counselling and Ethical Issues with Chromosome Microarray Analysis in Prenatal Testing”.

²²⁸ Lo, “Non-Invasive Prenatal Testing Using Massively Parallel Sequencing of Maternal Plasma DNA: From Molecular Karyotyping to Fetal Whole-Genome Sequencing”.

²²⁹ (Franklin 2013, p. 753)

²³⁰ Minear et al., “Noninvasive Prenatal Genetic Testing: Current and Emerging Ethical, Legal, and Social Issues”.

In the end, because prospective parents are often trying to make decisions about termination of pregnancy based on the results of prenatal diagnosis, there is a risk that the routinization of such tests could contribute to the selection and termination of pregnancies based on gender preference and genetic stigma. As such genomic technologies may be exploited for eugenic ends at the state level or at least contribute to a greater desire to have “perfect babies”²³¹.

Social impact of Direct To Consumer Genomic testing

One of the core concerns associated with the emergence of genetic testing technologies – particularly in the context of direct-to-consumer (DTC) testing – is that the information on genetic risk will cause harm²³².

“With the increasing public availability of a range of testing services, including tests for both relatively superficial traits such as athletic ability and those that disclose the risk of potentially serious diseases, many speculated that genetic test results could be misinterpreted, encourage unhealthy and fatalistic behavior, and cause anxiety.”²³³

Social impact of genome sequencing in public health

Ongoing advances in genomic sciences and technology have important implications for the understanding, prevention, and treatment of human disease. Most often, such developments are considered within the realm of clinical medicine (e.g. where we consider the patient-doctor scenario) but in public health, important transformations are also brought by the potential use of NGS in state-funded programs and “the increasing incorporation of genomics into population health sciences (genetic epidemiology, biostatistics, health policy, and health education)”²³⁴.

Newborn Screening Program (NBS)

NBS programs function at the intersection of public health, public policy and clinical care. These public health programs currently aim at “the early identification in asymptomatic newborns of conditions for which early and timely interventions can lead to the elimination or reduction of associated mortality, morbidity and disabilities”²³⁵. NGS could be used to increase the predictive value of NBS results²³⁶ but also to expand such programs by testing for many more disease-associated variants. Historically, the addition of disorders to state NBS panels has been slow and incremental but NGS may be employed to cover many more diseases and conditions than the ones currently tested²³⁷. As a practice that is already routine and mandatory for every one, NBS programs have been (contentiously) suggested as being a privileged place to implement whole genome sequencing, so that genomic data of each individual can be produced once and stored for a

²³¹ Garver and Garver, “The Human Genome Project and Eugenic Concerns.”; Duster, *Backdoor to Eugenics*.

²³² Niemiec, Kalokairinou, and Howard, “Current Ethical and Legal Issues in Health-Related Direct-to-Consumer Genetic Testing”.

²³³ Caulfield et al., “Harm, Hype and Evidence: ELSI Research and Policy Guidance”.

²³⁴ Roberts, Dolinoy, and Tarini, “Emerging Issues in Public Health Genomics”.

²³⁵ Howard et al., “Whole-Genome Sequencing in Newborn Screening? A Statement on the Continued Importance of Targeted Approaches in Newborn Screening Programmes”, p. 1593.

²³⁶ McCandless et al., “Sequencing from Dried Blood Spots in Infants with ‘False Positive’ Newborn Screen for MCAD Deficiency”.

²³⁷ Roberts, Dolinoy, and Tarini, “Emerging Issues in Public Health Genomics”.

lifetime²³⁸.

In the future, it may thus be possible that babies would be screened at birth, ‘to produce a comprehensive map of their key genetic markers, or even their entire genome’: ‘the baby’s genetic information could then be securely stored on their electronic patient record for future use. It could then be used throughout their lifetime to tailor prevention and treatment regimes to their needs as further knowledge becomes available about how our genes affect our risk of disease and our response to medicines’²³⁹. This perspective however raises a number of issues for NBS programs. First it is important to understand that the current NBS program uses biochemical tests for the screening phase, and genetic testing is only conducted once this phase shows an indication for a genetic test. For genomics sequencing to be used as a first tier screening approach would be problematic currently given the fact that we don’t know all the variants that cause disease in all populations. NGS could also provide unanticipated information (e.g., incidental findings including mutations associated with high risk for hereditary cancer syndromes) for infants who may have normal NBS results. “Some of that information, like carrier results, may not be immediately actionable for the child. Moreover, some of the information may be predictive, not diagnostic, and related to the onset of adult conditions”²⁴⁰. This situation could result in the labeling of a group of individuals, called “patients-in-waiting”, who are diagnosed with a disorder but are “waiting” for symptoms of their disorder to develop²⁴¹. These situations would be all the more complicated to manage when parents may not have consented to receive such information in mandatory NBS, where screening of infants does not necessarily require parental consent or notification.

From a practical point of view, the storage of extensive sets of genomic data on each individual within a population, their analysis and the potential updates required as well as their inclusion in medical files are technical and organizational challenges, which would question both the utility and cost-effectiveness of such endeavors²⁴².

Risk of misinterpretation of genetic/genomic information leading to psychological and social harms

Educating the public about public health genomic information is difficult especially since researchers are still determining its meaning across various contexts²⁴³. The complexity of most medical disorders makes it also difficult to understand and to explain how genetics interacts with several other factors that influence disease expression, such as health behaviors, environmental exposures, comorbid conditions, and social determinants of health. Communicating genetic information requires an ability to translate complicated findings to individuals who may lack the advanced skills in health literacy, numeracy, and genetic literacy that would be required to fully appreciate the meaning and implications of results. As such, the development of genomic technologies in public health cannot happen without planning to educate the public.

²³⁸ Goldenberg and Sharp, “The Ethical Hazards and Programmatic Challenges of Genomic Newborn Screening”.

²³⁹ Health, *Our Inheritance, Our Future. Realising the Potential of Genetics in the NHS*.

²⁴⁰ Roberts, Dolinoy, and Tarini, “Emerging Issues in Public Health Genomics”.

²⁴¹ Timmermans and Buchbinder, “Patients-in-Waiting: Living between Sickness and Health in the Genomics Era”.

²⁴² Roberts, Dolinoy, and Tarini, “Emerging Issues in Public Health Genomics”.

²⁴³ Ibid.

The tendencies in public opinion toward genetic exceptionalism and essentialism may impede this educational process because the label ‘genetic’²⁴⁴ is far from neutral and may result in genetic information being misinterpreted²⁴⁵.

“Given these nuances and sensitivities, genomic information in the clinic has ideally been suggested to be delivered by a trained genetic counselor with expertise in human genetics, health education, and interpersonal practice. Yet the traditional genetic counseling model—as developed for heritable, high penetrance adult-onset disorders—poses feasibility challenges given the need for extensive case preparation, comprehensive review of family and medical history information, and pre- and post-test education and counseling.”²⁴⁶

This model may not be practical from a public health perspective, especially as greater numbers of people require genetic services. Difficulties in conveying information in accurate and easily understood terms may lead to possible psychological and social harms in individuals receiving such information.

Discrimination from insurers and employers

Many prominent health policy challenges in public health genomics involve the regulation of access to genomic information generated by sequencing technologies. Besides its medical purposes, genetic information can also be used for nonmedical purposes, such as health or life insurance and employment purposes. Insurers might wish to use a genetic test result in the same way as they would use other medical or family history data. Employers might wish to ensure that an individual does not have a genetic risk which might affect his ability to work or which might lead to problems of safety. But being denied employment or insurance (or charged higher premiums on the basis of genetic traits), especially in times when welfare sectors are under increasing budgetary restrictions, are considered inequalities of treatments leading to discrimination of individuals or groups.

A number of international and national committees have developed recommendations for policy-makers to protect individuals against genetic discrimination. The UNESCO Universal Declaration on the Human Genome and Human Rights (1997) states that ‘*no one shall be subjected to discrimination based on genetic characteristics that is intended to infringe or has the effect of infringing human rights, fundamental freedoms and human dignity*’.

- The 1997 Council of Europe’s Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with Regard to the Applications of Biology and Medicine specifies in Article 11: ‘Any form of discrimination against a person on grounds of his or her genetic heritage is prohibited’. At the national level, the approaches used vary greatly²⁴⁷. *“In respect to insurance, three solutions are usually proposed: (1) prohibition of any use of genetic*

²⁴⁴ Ilklic, “Coming to Grips with Genetic Exceptionalism: Roots and Reach of an Explanatory Model”.

²⁴⁵ Ruiz-Canela, Valle-Mansilla, and Sulmasy, “What Research Participants Want to Know About Genetic Research Results: The Impact of ‘Genetic Exceptionalism’”.

²⁴⁶ Roberts, Dolinoy, and Tarini, “Emerging Issues in Public Health Genomics”.

²⁴⁷ Godard et al., “Genetic Information and Testing in Insurance and Employment: Technical, Social and Ethical Issues.”

*information by insurers outright; (2) legislation prohibiting this below a certain amount of coverage; and (3) moratoria; the adoption of moratoria on the use of genetic information has been a widespread response of the insurance industry throughout Europe. Among the countries where there is no regulation, bills have been presented or states that have ratified the 1997 Council of Europe's Convention are bound by it*²⁴⁸.²⁴⁹

- In the U.S., the federal Genetic Information Nondiscrimination Act (GINA) was passed in 2008, prohibiting health insurers and employers from using genetic information (including family history) to inform decisions about coverage, premiums, or hiring²⁵⁰. However, GINA does not cover life, disability, or long-term care insurance, which is important to note given the availability of genetic susceptibility testing for disorders like Alzheimer's disease²⁵¹.

Justice and Public Trust

The sector of public health is historically constructed with “the concern that health benefits and burdens be distributed fairly across the population. Yet many current genomic technologies used in health care are only available via specialty medical centers and not always covered by health insurers, limiting their access to significant proportions of the population, even in wealthy countries”²⁵². This evolution has serious consequences in terms of justice.

There is also a potential threat in terms of public trust with wildly optimistic forecasts as to the potential benefits of genomics in medicine and public health in a near future²⁵³.

Social issues related to genomic sequencing in Forensics

Since they have been developed, in the 1980s, forensic DNA profiling technologies have occupied increasing place in criminal, security, and mass disaster investigations²⁵⁴. NGS is now being introduced into routine criminal investigations and raises collective discussions about their social impact, especially since they have facilitated the introduction of a wide range of novel social institutions (such as forensic DNA databases and their governing bodies) as well as new stakeholders (such as the commercial providers of DNA hardware, software, and DNA analysis services) in the realm of surveillance and security.

Crime management

Technological innovation in forensic DNA profiling and the creation and maintenance of databases contributes to the expansion of the scientific toolbox available to law enforcement and may thus be perceived positively as contributing to the detection and conviction of criminal suspects²⁵⁵. Both the

²⁴⁸ I and Horstman, “European Practices of Genetic Information and Insurance: Lessons for the Genetic Information Nondiscrimination Act”.

²⁴⁹ Godard et al., “Genetic Information and Testing in Insurance and Employment: Technical, Social and Ethical Issues.”

²⁵⁰ Feldman, “The Genetic Information Nondiscrimination Act (GINA): Public Policy and Medical Practice in the Age of Personalized Medicine”.

²⁵¹ Taylor et al., “Genetic Testing For Alzheimer’s And Long-Term Care Insurance”.

²⁵² Roberts, Dolinoy, and Tarini, “Emerging Issues in Public Health Genomics”.

²⁵³ Brown, “Hope against Hype--Accountability in Biopasts, Presents and Futures”.

²⁵⁴ Williams and Wienroth, “Social and Ethical Aspects of Forensic Genetics: A Critical Review”.

²⁵⁵ Fraser and Williams, *Handbook of Forensic Science*.

increased access to ever-growing DNA databases and the investment in DNA-profiling technologies, is alledged “to further enhance the capacity of the police to use genetic information to detect suspects quickly and unequivocally”²⁵⁶, and should thus contribute to the detection and reduction of crime and an improvement in public safety ²⁵⁷.

*Acceptance of this argument by legislators and criminal justice agencies has led to a significant increase of biological samples — from crime scenes and individuals — being taken, stored, and used in those jurisdictions permitting the adopting of various kinds of DNA technologies. This increase has been accompanied by a widening of the categories of individuals subject to forensic profiling and analysis, and the expansion of jurisdictions’ adoption of DNA technologies globally. A further development under this perspective — fueled by the potential investigatory gains that may result from cross-border exchanges — is the emerging routine sharing of DNA profile data across national boundaries.*²⁵⁸

There are, however, voices that question the efficiency and reliability of genomic-led methods as data have proven to be difficult to capture and hard to interpret²⁵⁹ for well-established technologies, and even more for more recent innovations (such as familial searching, the use of ancestry-informative markers, and those that seek to infer externally visible characteristics from DNA samples)²⁶⁰.

Due process

DNA profiling may also be used to provide expert evidence in support of prosecution or defense cases in criminal trials. Determining whether this type of evidence is legit is challenging the courts. Among relevant issues to address are the representation of minorities in forensic databases²⁶¹ and the use of assumptions about the relationship between genetic and phenotypical characteristics.

Genetic surveillance

The expansion of forensic DNA profiling and databasing also supports new forms of biological surveillance of citizens, residents, visitors, and migrants²⁶². Questions are being raised about the governance of such uses, and in particular about which agencies will have access to DNA samples and profiles and for what purposes. At a time when the threat of terrorism accentuates security matters, these surveillance means may intervene in the definition of citizenship and the management of immigration ²⁶³.

²⁵⁶ Williams and Wienroth, “Social and Ethical Aspects of Forensic Genetics: A Critical Review”.

²⁵⁷ Townley and Ede, *Forensic Practice in Criminal Cases*.

²⁵⁸ Williams and Wienroth, “Social and Ethical Aspects of Forensic Genetics: A Critical Review”.

²⁵⁹ Williams and Weetman, “Enacting Forensics in Homicide Investigations”.

²⁶⁰ Williams and Wienroth, “Social and Ethical Aspects of Forensic Genetics: A Critical Review”.

²⁶¹ M’charek, “Technologies of Population: Forensic DNA Testing Practices and the Making of Differences and Similarities”.

²⁶² Toom, “Bodies of Science and Law : Forensic DNA Profiling , Biological Bodies , and Biopower”; Nelkin and Andrews, “DNA Identification and Surveillance Creep”; Duster, “The Molecular Reinscription of Race: Unanticipated Issues in Biotechnology and Forensic Science”.

²⁶³ M’charek, Schramm, and Skinner, “Topologies of Race: Doing Territory, Population and Identity in Europe”.

4.4 Technologies for modifying the genome – gene editing

As described in the previous section, the last few years have brought significant advancements in technologies used to modify DNA. In particular, systems like CRISPR-Cas9 have proven to be more efficient, precise and cheaper than previously used gene editing tools. While these new gene editing technologies open new possibilities, for example of curing diseases, many authors warn that their use (particularly in human germline) may negatively impact societies²⁶⁴. Below we describe (potential) economic and social impacts stemming from the use of gene editing technologies, with particular focus on the currently most promising tool, that is CRISPR-Cas9 and related tools. Below we describe: 1) the value of the gene editing market and economic impact of this technology; 2) (potential) benefits for society resulting from the use of the technology, 3) risks and concerns related to social impact associated with its use. These sections overlap to some extent, for example, some issues outlined under points 2) and 3) pertain also to economic impact.

We highlight here that since we focus on gene editing in humans, we cannot, for pragmatic reasons, address issues of gene editing in all organisms in this report. This means we do not address in any detail gene editing in plants, crops, livestock and other non-human animals, as well as in micro-organisms, regarding which the issue of dual-use becomes very pertinent. We, however, agree with authors who advise that we pay close attention to these areas as they are likely to impact humans sooner than later. (<http://embor.embopress.org/content/16/11/1421>)

4.4.1 Economic impact of gene editing technologies

We describe below the value of the gene editing market and some of its economic impacts. Much of what is present in this section is based on the information provided in a summary of Genome Editing/Genome Engineering Market report (2017) available on website of markets research company MarketsandMarkets²⁶⁵ and a report of Citi GPS Group²⁶⁶. Presented data encompass applications of various gene editing and engineering tools in a range of organisms, including non-human organisms. Currently the value of global gene editing and engineering market is estimated at USD 3,19 billion (as of 2017) and it is predicted to almost double this number in 5 years. The factors that stimulate the growth of gene editing market include, among others, governmental funding of gene editing studies and growing number of studies focusing on this technology, as well as prevalence of cancer and infectious diseases. Meanwhile, scarcity of professionals and negative perception among public of gene editing research may to some extent impede market development²⁶⁷.

Among end users of the technology, pharmaceutical and biotechnological companies seem to have the largest shares in the worldwide market of gene editing technologies. In terms of geographical distribution of the market, USA is expected to be the leader, followed by Europe²⁶⁸. CRISPR-Cas9, the

²⁶⁴ Dance, “Better Beings?”

²⁶⁵ Summary of Genome Editing/Genome Engineering Market report (2017), <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/genome-editing-engineering-market-231037000.html>

²⁶⁶ Citi GPS ‘Disruptive Innovations V. Ten more things to stop and think about’ (November 2017), <https://ir.citi.com/jWSPERuyU%2BxlRa193hvvnxNIYQzj4Rho%2F%2FfDXDHPNJOaeqhsfEnCzQ%3D%3D>

²⁶⁷ Summary of Genome Editing/Genome Engineering Market report (2017), <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/genome-editing-engineering-market-231037000.html>

²⁶⁸ Ibid.

newest of gene editing technologies, thanks to its unique features (see Section 3 for details) secured its leading position among other gene editing technologies in 2017²⁶⁹. Among various applications of gene editing technologies, cell lines modification is estimated to constitute the largest part of the market, which seems to be caused by increased awareness about stem cell therapies, and industry and government interest in stem cell research. Human therapeutics seems to be another very promising and potentially lucrative area of gene editing applications. Currently, there are a few ongoing clinical and preclinical trials of somatic gene editing (see Section 3 for details). Some predict that the first CRISPR therapy can be introduced to the market in around 6 years²⁷⁰.

Development of CRISPR-Cas9 industry may result in creation of additional workplaces, having therefore positive effect on job market. If gene editing tools will result in curing diseases, this may also have positive impact on economy, discussed briefly in the next Section 4.2.2.

Patents

Given the numerous applications of CRISPR-Cas9 and related revenues, ownership of rights to this technology has become a topic of high importance. Indeed, the creators of the technology: Jennifer Doudna (University of California) and Emmanuelle Charpentier (Max Plank Institute for Infection Biology in Berlin) on one side, and Zhang (the Broad Institute of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology and Harvard) on the other, entered a patent dispute. The dispute has been revolving mainly around the issues of who first invented the technology and what is the scope of each invention. As for now, as summed up by J. Sherkow:

“The present dispute has not stopped widespread licensing of critical patents, however, bringing with it an explosion of research from both academic and commercial sectors. Whether this broad availability will persist in the future remains uncertain.”²⁷¹.

As of January 2018, it appeared like the Broad Institute/MIT were the main winners of the dispute in the USA. This, however, is potentially not the case in Europe, where the European Patent Office has revoked the applications made by Broad/MIT due to mistakes and inconsistencies in their application documents²⁷².

Indeed, a number of companies emerged, some of which were (co)founded by the inventors of CRISPR-Cas9 or their institutions. These surrogate companies of the University of California, the Broad Institute and Emmanuelle Charpentier have been granted licences to their founders' patents²⁷³²⁷⁴. How much are these patents expected to generate for the patent owners and how much will these patents affect future use of the technology (for private gain or public good) remains unclear at the moment.

²⁶⁹ Ibid.

²⁷⁰ Citi GPS 'Disruptive Innovations V. Ten more things to stop and think about' (November 2017), <https://ir.citi.com/jWSPERuyU%2BxIRa193hvvNXYQzj4Rho%2F%2FfDXDHPNJOaqhsfEnCzQ%3D%3D>

²⁷¹ Sherkow, “The CRISPR Patent Landscape: Past, Present, and Future”.

²⁷² CRISPR patents, <http://www.crisprupdate.com/category/crispr-patents/>.

²⁷³ Ibid.

²⁷⁴ “How the battle lines over CRISPR were drawn” Jon Cohen Feb. 15, 2017. <https://www.sciencemag.org/news/2017/02/how-battle-lines-over-crispr-were-drawn>

4.4.2 Social impacts – potential benefits

Basic research

Such research is currently conducted in countries where legislation allows it

As described in Section 3, currently, in the area of human genetics, gene editing is used in basic research on human somatic cell lines and where allowed by law, also on human germline (embryos, eggs and sperm cells). In somatic human cells lines gene editing appears to be a powerful tool for exploration of gene function, disease development (e.g. cancer), drug invention, and development of somatic gene therapies²⁷⁵. Basic research using germline gene editing may contribute to general knowledge about the human embryo in its early stages of development, as well as provide information relevant to reproductive techniques (for example, *in vitro* fertilisation), and fuel studies on various diseases, including those aiming at developing new drugs. Should endeavours to apply germline gene editing in the clinic be ever deemed to be (legally and morally) permissible, the knowledge gained in basic research may also be of value in this context²⁷⁶.

Preclinical and clinical research and future clinical applications

Somatic gene editing

Preclinical research on somatic gene editing is currently performed. Clinical applications may occur in the future - first application of CRISPR-Cas9 in clinic is predicted to enter the markets in around 6 years²⁷⁷; other gene editing approaches may be used earlier. Please see Table 9 for examples of preclinical studies of gene editing for gene and cell therapy.

As described in Section 3, therapies based on somatic gene editing have been tested in a few clinical trials; some others are yet in preparation. Clearly, many of the diseases outlined in the previous section which are or may be targeted with CRISPR-Cas9 (or other similar tools) do not have, as of yet, a cure and are life-threatening. Therefore, the gene editing technology has the potential of providing a treatment or cure for a number of both genetic (which are often rare diseases) and non-genetic (e.g. AIDS) diseases and improve quality of life of relatively large group of individuals²⁷⁸. This would potentially also have a positive effect on the economy, if it increased ability to work of patients and eliminated or reduced the need for costly life-long treatment of patients. Indeed, the latter is only speculation at the moment as it could turn out that some somatic gene therapies are only treatments that must be regularly administered, and which are very costly.

Germline gene editing

Germline gene editing is not currently used in clinic. A few studies with an eye on clinical applications of germline gene editing have been conducted (see section 3.2.2 for details).

As described in Section 3, potential applications of germline gene editing in clinic may, in future, bring some advantages over currently used methods in specific situations. These situations include

²⁷⁵ Doudna and Charpentier, “The New Frontier of Genome Engineering with CRISPR-Cas9”.

²⁷⁶ Wert et al., “Responsible Innovation in Human Germline Gene Editing . Background Document to the Recommendations of ESHG and ESHRE”.

²⁷⁷ Citi GPS ‘Disruptive Innovations V. Ten more things to stop and think about’ (November 2017), <https://ir.citi.com/jWSPeruyU%2BxlRa193hvvNXIYQzi4Rho%2F%2FfDXDHPNJOaeqhsfEnCzQ%3D%3D>.

²⁷⁸ By definition in Europe, a rare disease affects less than 1/2000 ; meanwhile given the large numbers of rare diseases, it is estimated that collectively they affect hundreds of millions of persons currently.

the rare cases when a couple carry gene variant(s), which would certainly cause monogenic diseases in their offspring, and they for some reason cannot simply use pre-implantation genetic diagnosis, and they

- want to have genetically related offspring, and
- want to be sure that they will not pass the disease on to their offspring, and
- are willing to undergo IVF procedure.

In such cases, if considered safe to use, CRISPR-Cas9 (or similar tools) could be suggested to be used to correct single gene mutations in embryos carrying a disease-causing variant. The aim would be to cure the embryo and the subsequent individual who would develop from that embryo, as well as all her descendants, thereby reducing the burden of that disease over generations. In addition to this aim, germline gene editing has also been suggested as a way to correct mutations in embryos identified through PGD as having disease-causing variants. In this way, it has been argued that it could **increase the number of embryos eligible for transfer** for pregnancy. This suggestion, however is complicated by the (legal and/or biological and/or personal wished for) limits of transferring embryos into the owner. Whether this was supposed to apply to the wider context of embryo donations is unclear but this context is much more complex than simply having supposedly healthy embryos to donate. Moreover, when Ma et al. (2017), the authors of the first supposedly successful attempt at correcting a disease causing variant in viable human embryos (albeit there has been a lot of criticism of the study) suggested that by increasing number of “wild type” embryos for transfer to uterus, it would potentially increase pregnancy rates²⁷⁹, we can only assume that they meant for couples in the specific context described above. Indeed, in some very specific and rare situations, which involve all the conditions listed in points above, and when couples have specific configuration of genetic variants (please see Section 3 for details), gene editing could be the only method allowing couples to have genetically related children without passing the disease on to them.

Furthermore, some suggest that such practices of eliminating hypertrophic cardiomyopathy at the stage of embryos within IVF would be cheaper than providing care for persons affected by this disease²⁸⁰. Yet, to our knowledge there are no expert economic analysis indicating such an effect. Furthermore, the choice of “curing” this specific condition for which there is variable penetrance raises a lot of questions around what criteria would make diseases eligible for such approaches.

4.2.3 Social impacts – risks and concerns

Potential future use of germline gene editing in clinic **Safety and unpredictable effects**

The one publication presenting how CRISPR-Cas9 technology was used in human embryos in the research context seems to indicate that variants can be corrected with some degree of success, yet there still remains a lot of work to perfect this approach and to address the technical obstacles, that is, off-target effects, and mosaicism, as described in the previous Section 3. Therefore, safety remains

²⁷⁹ Ma et al., “Correction of a Pathogenic Gene Mutation in Human Embryos.”

²⁸⁰ Dance, “Better Beings?”

an important issue, which has yet to be resolved, before gene editing can be seriously considered for use in the clinic, as concluded in a number of expert societies recommendations and guidelines²⁸¹.

Yet, resolving the problems of off-target effects and mosaicism, will not guarantee that germline gene editing will be safe for the children which would be conceived with the use of this technology, as it is not possible to completely predict the impact of gene editing on a human organism without actually agreeing to have that human as part of the experiment. This is because, among others, gene editing constitutes quite invasive and complex integration in the genome as well as in the process of fertilization. Therefore, the first baby conceived using gene editing would be in a way part of a life-long experiment. Furthermore, offspring of the first “gene-edited” person would inherit the modification, subsequently passing it on the next generations. Effects of the technology on future generations are also difficult to predict. In long term perspective, application of heritable gene editing may eliminate certain (disease-causing) variants from the gene pool, which yet might appear beneficial in particular contexts²⁸². An example of such an effect, can be an allele causing sickle-cell anaemia, which was shown also to give resistance for malaria. Yet, for many other variants causing unwanted effects, we may not yet be aware of their “positive” effect, which may manifest in currently unknown particular genetic background and/or environment²⁸³.

Furthermore, the general research burden needed to get to the answer of whether germ-line gene editing would ever be “safe enough” given the alternatives we currently have, should be seriously questioned. The minimum amount of research needed to get to that point is already rife with ELSI. In the Ma et al. (2017) study alone, hundreds of embryos were developed, and many more eggs were collected from female donors who were financially compensated for this donation. This raises ethical issues around consent (and coercion) of donors, of whether the benefits of the research outweigh the very concrete risks of developing ovarian Hyper-Stimulation Syndrome (OHSS) (which has a 6% risk per cycle) and the inequalities in burden between the male and female donors. Moreover, the governance of allowing embryos to grow beyond 14 days in the laboratory would have to be completely revised²⁸⁴, and importantly there would have to be extremely careful regulation around all the “experiments” conducted leading up to and including the birth of such a child.

Justice and potential social disparities

Furthermore, germline gene editing may impact not only phenotypes of many human generations but may also trigger **unexpected social changes**.

As explained in the section above (on potential benefits of germline gene editing and in Section 3) germline gene editing would be applied in very specific situations, that is, in the context of *in vitro* fertilization, to fulfil a desire to have genetically related child, and at the same time avoid passing a given disease on a child. As indicated by some, the desire to have genetically related child, and even of having a child in general does not necessarily constitute a right (in and of itself) and as such may

²⁸¹ Wert et al., “Human Germline Gene Editing . Recommendations of ESHG”; National Academies of Sciences and Medicine, “Human Genome Editing: Science, Ethics, and Governance”; Ormond et al., “Human Germline Genome Editing”.

²⁸² Dance, “Better Beings?”

²⁸³ Ibid.

²⁸⁴ Some have already proposed changes to the 14-days rule, for example: Harris, John, “It’s time to extend the 14-day limit for embryo research”, *The Guardian*, 6 May, 2016, available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2016/may/06/extend-14-day-limit-embryo-research>

not be a need which should be fulfilled as a part of services offered within public healthcare system²⁸⁵, and one could further argue whether public money should go towards refining the technique. Consequently, offering germline gene editing in such context raises questions about the **just allocation of resources** within a healthcare system. Offering germline gene editing as part of public healthcare services may result in potentially “*unjustified draining of resources from more pressing (albeit less novel) therapies*”²⁸⁶.

Even if germline gene editing would be offered outside of a public healthcare system, such a commercial offer would also raise issues related to social justice. Gene editing services, if available only to financially privileged in society, might create disparities, a type of **social stratification**, whereby rich people endow their progeny with “enhanced” genome creating, consequently, a population non-affected by certain diseases. Some refer to such a phenomenon consumer eugenics²⁸⁷. One may argue that such division in societies is already present nowadays, where many unprivileged groups do not have access to basic medical care, while others take advantage of sophisticated medical procedures of sometimes questionable utility. Yet, germline gene editing might potentially deepen such disparities²⁸⁸. Such a division could be even more apparent when gene editing would be used for enhancement purposes. Currently such applications are still rather far-fetched, as many traits have complex genetic background, and gene editing is currently applied mainly to monogenic diseases²⁸⁹. However, such applications cannot be excluded in the future. Discussions on enhancement uses of gene editing bring important questions such as where the line should be drawn between applications for treatment and curing purposes and enhancement; some indicate that these two areas may be difficult if not impossible to delineate²⁹⁰.

Instrumentalization of embryos and persons participating in germline gene editing

Disparities-causing impact of gene editing may have yet another dimension. As put by Howard et al. (2017):

*“If heritable gene editing was allowed, how would the fact that for the first time, a human (scientist or clinician) would be directly editing the nuclear DNA of another human in a heritable way cause some form of segregation of types of humans? Creators and the created?”*²⁹¹

These questions posed by Howard et al. and previously raised by Margaret Somerville²⁹² seem to relate to the issue of **instrumentalization of human embryos** and potentially also persons conceived with use of gene editing; experiment of gene editing would in a way continue through their whole

²⁸⁵ Denier, “Need or Desire? A Conceptual and Moral Phenomenology of the Child Wish”.

²⁸⁶ Howard et al., “One Small Edit for Humans, One Giant Edit for Humankind? Points and Questions to Consider for a Responsible Way Forward for Gene Editing in Humans”.

²⁸⁷ Dance, “Better Beings?”

²⁸⁸ Ibid.

²⁸⁹ Ibid.

²⁹⁰ Howard et al., “One Small Edit for Humans, One Giant Edit for Humankind? Points and Questions to Consider for a Responsible Way Forward for Gene Editing in Humans”.

²⁹¹ Ibid.

²⁹² Debating the ethics of gene editing, <http://www.cbc.ca/radio/the180/gene-editing-debating-the-usefulness-of-sci-fi-analogies-and-does-more-parental-leave-actually-help-women-1.3351174/debating-the-ethics-of-gene-editing-1.3351261>

lives²⁹³. Obviously, such “research subjects” in a life-long gene editing study would not have been asked for **informed consent** (as the experiment would be performed at the stage of embryos). “Creators”, as framed above include those who would decide that future generation would be genetically modified, including not just parents but also others in power, those doing the actual modifying. One may say that currently, there are many types of decisions that are routinely taken by parents on behalf of (unborn) children²⁹⁴, for example in prenatal health interventions, or when choosing a school etc. However, in such situations there is either consensus that these interventions are in best interest of a child or they are reversible, unlike it would be in the case of gene editing. Thus, as noted by Smolenski (2015):

“Such [germline gene editing] modifications cannot be seen as a natural extension of those parental interventions that we currently accept. Additionally, we permit parents to intervene on their children’s behalf based on the presumption that they are doing so to confer some sort of benefit, and many countries have laws prohibiting nonbeneficial interventions, even when parents strongly desire them.”²⁹⁵

Moreover, as noted by Sheila Jasanoff (the Harvard Kennedy School of Government in Cambridge, Massachusetts):

“You are not only modifying someone, but depriving that person’s progeny of a kind of open-endedness about their futures that all of humanity, potentially, is entitled to expect”²⁹⁶

This idea of and support for an open future for children is not new, and is regularly addressed regarding the conservative approach for genetic testing for susceptibilities in minors.

The term “designer babies”, often used in media reports on gene editing, seem to point out a caveat related to **instrumentalization** of embryos and, as some authors indicate, children. The term “designer babies”, in the context of gene editing and particularly when discussing potential (and now rather far-fetched) enhancement uses, refers to children who would have undergone germline gene editing in order to have genetic makeup desired by their parents. Some authors, for example Savulescu and Kahane, argue that

“couples who decide to have a child have a significant moral reason to select the child who, given his or her genetic endowment, can be expected to enjoy the most well-being”.²⁹⁷

Meanwhile, another author points out caveats of such approach:

“In caring for the health of their children, parents do not cast themselves as designers or convert their children into products of their will or instruments of their ambition. The same cannot be said of parents who pay large sums to select the sex of their child (for nonmedical reasons) or who aspire to bioengineer their child’s intellectual endowments or athletic prowess.”²⁹⁸

²⁹³ Smolenski, “CRISPR/Cas9 and Germline Modification: New Difficulties in Obtaining Informed Consent”.

²⁹⁴ Ibid.

²⁹⁵ Ibid.

²⁹⁶ Dance, “Better Beings?”

²⁹⁷ Savulescu and Kahane, “The Moral Obligation to Create Children with the Best Chance of the Best Life”.

²⁹⁸ Sandel, *The Case against Perfection: Ethics in the Age of Genetic Engineering*.

Not only potential clinical application of gene editing in clinic, but also basic and preclinical research on gene editing in germline raises issues of social justice. Such research on human embryos utilizes and destroys embryos, which are technically human beings in the earliest stage of their development. Therefore, their destruction is problematic and many states have legislations in place restricting or prohibiting such uses of embryos for research, which are rooted mainly in respect for human dignity²⁹⁹. The Oviedo Convention also states that research on human embryos requires special protection and prohibits creation of embryos for purposes of research³⁰⁰. Yet, for research on germline gene editing “freshly-created” embryos are particularly valuable. Such kind of research, as mentioned above, requires egg donation, which involves invasive and risky procedures to retrieve eggs. Women who participate in such studies are often compensated, which raises issues of their coercion and **exploitation**, as mainly women in financial need would decide for such procedures.

Impact on people with disabilities

The issue of criteria which would be set to decide which disorders and traits may be eradicated/enhanced brings another question of the potential **impact on people with these disorders or disabilities**. Allowing eradication of these disabilities by gene editing, may give impression that people with certain disabilities are not desired in a society, an impact which have been already discussed in the context of NIPT³⁰¹. Meanwhile, research exploring views of disabled people reveals that many of them perceive their life as having good or excellent quality³⁰². Furthermore, some indicate that eliminating disabled people from societies may reduce opportunities for our society, for example, to learn compassion³⁰³. Consequently, questions of which criteria should and should not be applied to choose which traits and diseases can be targeted by gene editing seem to be even more relevant.

Somatic gene editing

Do it yourself gene editing - self-experimentation with somatic gene editing

In Section 3.2.2 we described a case of a biohacker who injected himself with CRISPR system. The biohacker suggested that given the availability of the gene engineering tools, their use is going to be increasingly common. Moreover, he suggested that deciding about one’s own genotype is a human right:

“The point is that we are on the cusp of humanity changing. This is the first of many people who will change their genomes. This will happen for medical reason, for science, athletics or maybe just because people wanted to or were bored. (...) What could be more of a human right than to be able to decide what genes create you?” ³⁰⁴

²⁹⁹ Isasi and Knoppers, “Mind the Gap: Policy Approaches to Embryonic Stem Cell and Cloning Research”.

³⁰⁰ Council of Europe, *Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with Regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine: Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine*.

³⁰¹ Kellogg et al., “Attitudes of Mothers of Children with Down Syndrome towards Noninvasive Prenatal Testing”.

³⁰² Albrecht and Devlieger, “The Disability Paradox: Highly Qualified of Life against All Odds”.

³⁰³ Dance, “Better Beings?”

³⁰⁴ <http://www.ifyoudontknownowyknow.com/2017/10/the-first-human-to-attempt-crispr-gene.html>

Josiah Zayner is not the only biohacker who tested a new technology on himself, other cases of self-experimentation have been recently reported³⁰⁵. Indeed, do-it-yourself science movement seems to be growing. Kits to engineer bacteria with CRISPR systems can be bought online³⁰⁶. This kind of do it yourself science can have educational value as well may result in increased interest of public in the current research. On the other hand, although currently available, do-it-yourself gene editing kits are not designed to be used in humans, some may attempt to do this, which may be potentially risky for health. Secondly, the questions arise about the impact on environment of such home-made bacteria modifications, in case they are not properly utilized and realised to environment.

³⁰⁵ 'A Biohacker Regrets Publicly Injecting Himself With CRISPR'
<https://www.theatlantic.com/science/archive/2018/02/biohacking-stunts-crispr/553511/>

³⁰⁶ The Odin, <http://www.the-odin.com/>

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